

Cruise Report AR76-01 (AR2307)
The BAffin Bay Deglacial Experiment (BADEX)

Woods Hole, MA to Nuuk, Greenland
R/V Neil Armstrong
July 11th – August 13th, 2023

A US National Science Foundation Funded Project

Oregon State University
College of Earth, Ocean,
and Atmospheric Sciences

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Acknowledgements

This cruise was supported by grants from the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF). The awards covered ship time for the *R/V Neil Armstrong* and institutional support to Hatfield (#2112536), Reilly (#2300114), Klotsko (#2112529), Jennings (#2112547), and Walczak (#2112498). Additional physical, logistical, and personnel support was provided by the MARine Sediment SAMpling Group (MARSSAM) at Oregon State University and the Oregon State University Marine and Geology Repository (OSU-MGR). Both MARSSAM and the OSU-MGR are NSF supported resources through awards #1823565 and #2310875, respectively. The coring equipment was supplied by MARSSAM, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI), and the University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) equipment pool. At sea operations were conducted in Greenlandic and Canadian territorial waters adjacent to Labrador and Nunavut Inuit Lands.

The success of the cruise strongly depended on several groups of people at different phases of the project. In the pre-cruise planning phase, the efforts of Kerry Strøm, Sarah Fuller, and Finnick (Finn) Morrison at WHOI were invaluable in guiding us through the scheduling, permitting, and planning process. At sea, we were indebted to Captain Kent Sheasley and Mates Diego Gevaudan, Mariah Kopec-Belliveau, and Christina (Chrissy) Hogan for their operational skills in a challenging sea-ice environment. We would not have accomplished half of the science goals without their unwavering commitment to our project. We also need to thank SSSG's Emily Cheung and Sonia Brugger, Bosun Peter (Pete) Liarikos and Night Bosun Keenan Foley, Steward Harold (Harry) Burnett, and the rest of the crew and staff onboard the *R/V Neil Armstrong* for enhancing our experience at sea.

Finally, we would like to thank our shore-based spouses, partners, children, and friends for their support so we could spend five plus weeks at sea away from home to pursue our research.

The R/V Armstrong, whose crew went above and beyond in the name of science. Photos: R.V. Kelleher.

Recommended Citation

Hatfield R.G., Klotsko S., Reilly B.T., Jennings A.E., Mix A.C., Stoner J.S., Walczak M.H., Donnenfield J., Fritz C., Gregory E., Hough A., Kelleher R., Monito L., Olarte P., Siragusa M., Stelling K., and Vonnahme T.R., 2023. *R/V Neil Armstrong Expedition AR76-01 (AR2307), The Baffin Bay Deglacial Experiment (BADEX)*, July 11 – August 13, 2023. 592 p. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10278217

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Executive Summary

AR76-01 was a 33-day expedition of R/V *Neil Armstrong* in support of the Baffin Bay Deglacial Experiment (BADEX) to the western Labrador slope and Baffin Bay. The cruise began in Woods Hole, MA on July 11th, 2023 and ended in Nuuk, Greenland on August 13th, 2023. The shipboard science party included participants from the University of Florida, Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory, the University of North Carolina Wilmington, Oregon State University, the University of Colorado Boulder, the Greenland Climate Research Center, the University of Central Florida, and the University Centre of Westfjords. The cruise was led by three early career, pre-tenured, assistant professors, half of the science berths were staffed by a post-doc and graduate students, and over half of the science party identified as female. Support for the expedition came from the US National Science Foundation.

Our primary goal was to identify and sample sedimentary deposits suitable to reconstruct the mechanisms and processes involved in initiating and sustaining the large-scale deglaciation of a marine-terminating ice sheet. Our central hypothesis asserted that increasing subsurface ocean temperature at the grounding line of marine terminating glaciers is a primary driver of ice-sheet instability. To test this hypothesis required a unified program of geophysical seafloor mapping, sub-seafloor imaging, biological and water sampling, and sediment coring.

Over the course of 33-days at sea we occupied 27 stations and sampled five major trough mouth fan systems spanning 9 degrees of latitude in Baffin Bay. Shipboard data and physical sample collection were given the sample prefix AR2307 and included multibeam bathymetry, Chirp subbottom data, plankton net tows, CTD casts and hydro-casts (Niskin bottle rosette sampling), and multi-core, gravity, and piston coring. In total, 109 deployments were made from the ship. These deployments comprise; 20 phytoplankton and zooplankton tows, 20 CTDs and water samples, 11 multicores (MC), 45 gravity cores (GC), 13 trigger cores (TC), and 13 jumbo piston cores (JC). In total 396.15 meters of sediment was collected, and 2,520 liters of water was sampled. Phytoplankton experiments were conducted on the ship, water samples were filtered for biomarkers and radiogenic isotopes, and the gravity and piston cores were CT-imaged and measured on a multi-sensor core logger. A subset of the cores were split, imaged, and described at sea when time and resources allowed. All geological samples were curated at the Oregon State University Marine and Geology Repository (OSU-MGR) following the expedition.

A Note on Report Organization

The findings of this report are organized chronologically by deployment number from operations on the Labrador slope during the first week of transit, to operations within Nuup Kangerlua during the last few hours of the cruise. Deployment numbers were assigned incrementally whenever a wire went out over the side of the ship. Several different deployments can be grouped together in a station which encompasses several operations at a single location. New station numbers were assigned incrementally when the ship was moved a significant enough distance that a different geomorphic target was being studied. Several stations are grouped into a region and together eight regions comprise the results of this cruise. Following a general introduction and methods section, the report structure begins with the background to each region and is followed by a summary of the geophysical surveying of that region, and a description of the operations at each station. A summary of methods is provided in this report, but extended methodological descriptions can be found in Appendix 1. CTD data and underway data can be found in Appendix 2. Chirp images for each station and CT-scan images, Line scan images, Multi Sensor

Track (MST) data, and core description summaries for each of the recovered cores can be found in Appendix 3. Core description log sheets can be found in Appendix 4. Coring data sheets can be found in Appendix 5.

A Note on Project Nomenclature

In this report, elements of this project are referred to as BADEX, AR76-01, and AR2307.

BADEX is the science program that encompasses all elements of the experimental design, field program, post cruise science, and data synthesis. BADEX largely revolves around the cruise reported here, but also a number of legacy samples/data and post-cruise initiatives. The BADEX research program will extend for many years beyond the field program, and we hope that the BADEX science team will continue to grow.

AR76-01 is the official cruise designation given by the ship operator, WHOI, and indicates the ship (AR), the number of times this ship has been to its home port (76), and the cruise number since the last time the ship was in its home port (01). This is the nomenclature that should be used when referring to the cruise itself.

AR2307 is the prefix given to samples recovered during AR76-01 and conforms to the standard set by the OSU-MGR, indicating the ship (AR), the year the cruise took place (23), and the month that the cruise began (07). For example, the 85th over-the-side operation of Cruise AR76-01 (which was a jumbo piston core) has a sample name of AR2307-85JC.

BADEX is the name of the science program. Leo is the name of our fearless winch operator. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly

There are several terms used colloquially in our data sheets and notes that might differ from the more formal report here. For example, in our notes we often refer to the “WHOI GC,” which is technically the gravity corer that lives on the R/V Armstrong and more appropriately should be called the “Armstrong gravity core.” Similarly, we often refer to the “piston core bomb” or “WHOI JPC bomb” which is in reference to the solid 5,000 lb weight at the top of the piston core. This weight differs from the “weight stand” of the trigger core and Armstrong gravity core, which is a stack of removable weights on the tops of each of those devices. In our data sheets, we refer to plankton net deployments as “NT” for “Net Tow;” however, there were actually two devices in each of these deployments and the samples from each device have been labeled “PP” for the “Phytoplankton Net” and “ZP” for the “Zooplankton Net” (e.g. deployment AR2307-82NT in the log and datasheets actually has two sets of samples named AR2307-82PP and AR2307-82ZP for the two different nets used in the deployment). This PP/ZP nomenclature is what we use throughout this report and is consistent with the convention we use to label the piston cores and trigger cores as two separate devices from the same deployment (e.g. AR2307-85TC and AR2307-85JC).

A view inside the coring shack. Much (if not all) of what we were able to sample from the bottom of the ocean was only possible due to the extensive project planning, execution, and equipment and logistical support from the MARine Sediment SAMpling group (MARSSAM) at Oregon State University. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

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*Table 1: List of science team members, their role or specialism, and institutional affiliation. *Shore based scientists.*

Introduction

Motivation

Projecting changes in the volume of Earth's remaining ice sheets is a source of uncertainty in the projections of future sea-level rise. Marine terminating ice margins are the most vulnerable to a warming climate and impactful for rapid sea-level rise (IPCC et al., 2013). The advection of relatively warm ocean water to submarine grounding zones (Holland et al., 2008; Straneo et al., 2012) is hypothesized to lead to ice-shelf thinning, grounding zone retreat, and potential unstable collapse (Alley et al., 2015, 2007; Pollard et al., 2015; Scambos et al., 2017; Schoof, 2007). However, instrumental observations do not extend far enough into the past to develop a robust understanding of how, and why, a previously stable marine terminating ice sheet begins and continues to retreat (Scambos et al., 2017).

We can learn much about deglacial triggering from the behavior of past glacial retreat. During the global Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; 26.5-19 ka; (Clark et al., 2009) the Greenland Ice Sheet (GIS) extended westward into Baffin Bay, was grounded near the continental shelf break (Dowdeswell et al., 2014; Hofmann et al., 2018; Hogan et al., 2016; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2013a, 2013b 2018; Sheldon et al., 2016; Slabon et al., 2016, 2018), and was likely fringed with floating ice shelves and perennial sea-ice (Jennings et al., 2018, 2017; Knutz et al., 2011) with some evidence for a larger ice shelf covering northernmost Baffin Bay (Couette et al., 2022; Ownsworth et al., 2023), somewhat similar to conditions observed in Antarctica today (Scambos et al., 2017). This expanded margin was fed and maintained by a series of ice streams that generated and delivered large volumes of sediment to the continental slope. From this quasi-equilibrium LGM configuration, the GIS became unstable and retreated landward in a series of pauses and reversals by the early-middle Holocene (Hogan et al., 2016; Sheldon et al., 2016; Slabon et al., 2016).

Previous geophysical surveying and sediment coring efforts in eastern Baffin Bay have primarily focused on the Greenland continental shelf and have constrained where the ice sheet was located as it began to retreat (Hofmann et al., 2018; Hogan et al., 2016; Jennings et al., 2014; Newton et al., 2017; Sheldon et al., 2016; Slabon et al., 2016). However, shelf-based observations are unable to offer insight into the conditions that existed prior to, and during, destabilization. To understand these early triggers of ice retreat we must look beyond the shelf edge, to the continental slope, seaward of the paleo-margins of the marine-based GIS. The BADEX project built on geophysical survey data that suggested hemipelagic slope deposits exist near most west Greenland TMF systems (Dorschel et al., 2017) and per comm. 2020) and on feasibility studies of existing cores that indicated that these sediments contain co-registered proxies of ice sheet retreat and past ocean conditions (Jackson et al., 2017; Jennings et al., 2018, 2017).

The AR76-01 cruise of the BADEX project targeted fine-grained sediment deposits on the Labrador margin and the northern flanks of four TMF systems in Baffin Bay along a transect from Melville Bugt to Disko Bugt (Stations 7 through 24; Figure 1; Table 3). This strategy provided the opportunity to compare latitudinal, geological, and geomorphic variations with reconstructions of paleo-ice margin behavior and paleoceanographic conditions. Where sediments and ice conditions allowed, we targeted sediment packages from the upper to lower continental slope to enable a vertical reconstruction of water masses and changes in ocean circulation that may influence periods of ice retreat. A station in the Labrador Sea (Station 1) provided an opportunity to sample an expanded glacial sequence that could offer a

chronostratigraphic template for sediments within Baffin Bay. Several stations in Davis Strait (Stations 2 through 5) afforded characterization of the southern part of Baffin Bay and Davis Strait, though recovery of fine-grained sediments was difficult along this part of the margin. Station 6 presented itself opportunistically to recover sediments from a small basin between the Upernavik and Uumannaq TMF systems.

Figure 1: Bathymetric map of Baffin Bay and ship track lines showing the locations of Stations 2 through 24 that were occupied during AR76-01. TMF = Trough Mouth Fan.

Physical and Oceanographic Setting of the West Greenland Shelf

The west Greenland continental shelf extends from Davis Strait to Nares Strait and separates continental Greenland from the deep central basin of Baffin Bay. Several large cross shelf troughs extend from the coastal fjords to the shelf break (Jakobsson et al., 2000, 2020; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2013a, 2013b, 2018; Slabon et al., 2016, 2018) – see Figure 1. The seafloor morphology and sedimentary successions of these troughs bear the imprint of fast flowing ice streams that repeatedly occupied and deepened these depressions during successive full-glacials of the Pleistocene (Hofmann et al., 2016, 2018; Hogan et al., 2016; Knutz et al., 2019; Newton et al., 2017; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2018; Sheldon et al., 2016; Slabon et al., 2016, 2018). These troughs, and the ice streams within them, were conduits for the delivery of large volumes of lithogenic detritus to the upper continental slope via glacigenic debris flows, turbid meltwater plumes, and iceberg rafted detritus (IRD). This resulted in the progradation of extensive, outward-bulging TMF systems (Ó Cofaigh et al., 2003; Hofmann et al., 2018, 2016; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2013a; Vorren and Laberg, 1997) that, along with the troughs, are clearly visible in the seafloor bathymetry (Figure 1).

The generalized ocean circulation in Baffin Bay is counterclockwise with water sourced from both the Arctic and Atlantic oceans (Tang et al., 2004). The West Greenland Current (WGC) enters Baffin Bay through Davis Strait and is composed of the low salinity, cold, polar waters of the East Greenland Current (EGC) and the warm, saline Atlantic waters of the Irminger Current that converge south of Greenland. In summer, the upper ~50 m of the water column typically has a salinity (S) < 31 that warms to about 9 °C on the eastern edge of the Labrador Sea off SW Greenland and to about 4 °C in northern Baffin Bay. Below this, subzero, low salinity ($S \sim 33.5-34$), Arctic Surface Water (ASW) forms a near-surface layer (roughly 50-300m depth) over most of Baffin Bay; equivalent layers off SW Greenland are saltier (S 34.5-34.8) but warmer (3-4 °C) (Ribergaard et al., 2008). Beneath this cold layer is relatively warm and salty Atlantic Water that originates in the Irminger Current (Buch, 2000a, 2000b). Atlantic Water bathes the continental shelf and slope and flows northwards as West Greenland Intermediate Water (WGIW) at a depth of ~300-700 m (diffused across depths but with flows constrained by the ~640m sill depth at Davis Strait; Azetsu-Scott et al., 2012). WGIW has temperatures of about 5 °C off SW Greenland, falling to about 2-3 °C in northern Baffin Bay as it is diluted with colder northern waters. At depths > ~1200m is Deep Baffin Bay Water, which fills the basin north of Davis Strait with water temperatures of ~0 °C. The modern sea ice edge extends southwest to northeast within Baffin Bay, marking the boundary between northern sources of low salinity ASW and the southerly inflowing warm and saline WGC (Münchow et al., 2015; Tang et al., 2004; Zeidan et al., 2022).

BADEX Experimental Design and Key Scientific Questions

The BADEX was designed to test our key hypothesis, “Increasing subsurface ocean temperature at the grounding line of marine terminating glaciers as a primary driver of ice-sheet instability”. The work plan includes methods to understand GIS variability, timing of change, the role of the ocean, and regional integration (Figure 2).

Major Hypothesis:

Increasing subsurface ocean temperature at the grounding line of marine terminating glaciers is a primary driver of ice-sheet instability.

Figure 2: Diagram illustrating the experimental design of the BADEX program.

We aimed to address the following key scientific questions through this experimental design:

- How stable was the western margin of the GIS (wGIS) during the global LGM (23-19 ka; Mix et al., 2001), prior to shelf edge retreat?
- What was the extent and nature of wGIS glaciation during the late Pleistocene? Were ice shelves present and, if so, what were their extents?
- What was the timing of wGIS shelf edge retreat? Was retreat synchronous along the margin?
- Were standstills and/or re-advances in wGIS deglacial retreat influenced by large scale abrupt climate changes such as the Younger Dryas?
- How did Baffin Bay circulation, water masses, and sea ice evolve from the LGM through the deglaciation?
- What were the oceanographic, atmospheric, glaciological, and bathymetric factors that triggered the transition from a stable LGM marine terminating ice sheet to a retreating ice sheet along the wGIS?

We also sought to address additional, but complementary, questions during Cruise AR76-01 to help better understand both modern oceanography and paleo-proxies, including:

- How did the geomagnetic field change regionally during the late Pleistocene and how can those changes be leveraged for high-resolution stratigraphic correlation?

- What are the modern distributions of radiocarbon, stable isotopes, neodymium, biomarkers, foraminifera, and other microfossils in Baffin Bay surface sediments and water column profiles?
- What is the vertical and horizontal variability of primary production in Baffin Bay distal to west Greenland fjords?
- What are the sedimentary, oceanographic, and glacial processes that shape continental slope deposits and features in Baffin Bay? How did these differ along the margin?

Science Methods

Geophysical Surveying

Multibeam

Two Kongsberg multibeam systems were used for bathymetric surveying. The EM710 was used for shallow surveys, up to 1800m water depth. The EM122 was used for deeper water surveys, with water depths ranging from 500-3300m. When the water depth fit in both the EM710 and EM122 range, both instruments were run concurrently. Data were collected with Seafloor Information Systems (SIS) software, which displayed both, real-time bathymetric data and previously collected data. HydrOffice Sound Speed software was used to apply XBT casts, CTD casts, and interpolated transit sound speed to the multibeam systems. Corrections were applied to the multibeam data to account for heading, heave, yaw, pitch, and roll based on the shipboard inertial measurement unit (IMU) using an Applanix POSMV.

CHIRP

A Knudsen Engineering model 3260 3.5 kHz / 12 kHz Compressed High Intensity Radar Pulse (CHIRP) subbottom profiler was used to survey the upper sediment layers of the seafloor. Depending on the composition of the seafloor, this system could image anywhere between 0~45 m below the seafloor during AR76-01. The program assumed a seawater sound speed velocity of 1500 m/s. The system used a 16x16 element transducer array. The 3.5 kHz signal with a 2-kHz bandwidth was the most informative channel for our purposes, so the 12 kHz was kept off. Surveys were completed at a speed of 6 kts or slower, often due to sea ice causing the slower speeds. During surveys, we varied power and pulse length depending on water depth to improve resolution and penetration. Ping rate varied based on pulse length, but had a maximum of 500 ms. Data was recorded in Binary Ascii Segy format and RAW files (.kea files and .keb files) and were saved to the shipboard data server.

XBT

Expendable Bathythermographs (XBTs) were launched while underway. We used three different Lockheed Martin XBT Models T-4 (max depth 460 m), T-5 (max depth 1830 m), and T-7 (max depth 760 m) and selected the model appropriate to the water depth we were in. XBT temperature profiles were used to inform sound velocity profiles, which influence the quality and accuracy of multibeam bathymetry and backscatter. During transit, XBT's were taken once every 24 hours. While surveying, XBT's were run every 6 hours or more depending on varying speed, depth, and conditions. XBT temperature profiles were recorded in WinMK21 software before being imported to the multibeam data into the Seafloor Information System (SIS) software via sound speed manager software.

Co-Chief Scientist Shannon Klotsko at the “control center” of the RV Armstrong main lab looking for the perfect core site that would ultimately be located under heavy sea-ice. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly

Biological Sampling and Water Sampling

Plankton Tows

Paired phytoplankton (25 cm diameter, 20 μm mesh, KC Denmark) and zooplankton (50cm diameter, 150 μm mesh, Sea-Net) vertically integrated net hauls were performed at each major station first from 300-0 m depth, and then from 60-0m depth. The two nets were deployed on a frame to sample the identical water column at the same time and weighted using a ~ 25 lb weight. The wire was the same 3/8-inch diameter steel wire and winch system used for the Armstrong Gravity Core. Phytoplankton were sampled from the smaller net via a cod-end valve and preserved in Lugol’s Solution (iodine). Zooplankton were washed from a removable cod-end on the larger net into 500cc jars and were preserved in 10% formalin buffered with borax (see extended methods in Appendix 1).

Frame mounted zooplankton (larger) and phytoplankton (smaller) nets deployed during AR76-01. The frame was weighted by a lump of concrete connected with an eye bolt. Photo credit: A.C. Mix.

CTD and Hydrocasts

R/V *Neil Armstrong's* standard Seabird SBE 9+ CTD with dual sets of Temperature and Conductivity sensors, 24 10L Niskin bottles, and auxillary sensors (Oxygen, CDOM, turbidity, transmissometer, fluorometer, altimeter) was modified by removing 3 bottles (bottle numbers 14-16) to make room for the WHOI Multidisciplinary Instrumentation in Support of Oceanography (MISO) Camera and lighting system. The CTD was deployed using the conducting .322 cable from the starboard side which allows for live transmission of CTD data and low resolution still images during deployment. High resolution images from the MISO camera were retrieved after the operation. The CTD system was deployed at each of the major stations either before or after the plankton net tows. CTD casts occurred before any sediment coring or after moving the ship away from a sediment coring location to prevent sediment introduced to the water column from contaminating Niskin bottle water column samples. Each CTD cast descended to just above the sea floor (navigated using the altimeter), so that the MISO camera system could image the sea floor environment. Niskin Bottles were triggered at depths of interest during the upcast, and subsampled after recovery (for further information please see extended methods in Appendix 1).

The CTD and Niskin bottle rosette used over the course of AR76-01 being deployed close to the sea ice edge to, in part, catch those little plankton seeing sunlight for the first time in months. Photo credit: R.V. Kelleher.

Coring Operations

All sediment coring operations were led by the Oregon State University MARSSAM group and focused on the collection of multi-cores using the 8-tube MC-800, gravity cores, and jumbo piston/trigger cores.

Multicores (MC)

Multicoring on AR76-01 utilized the MC-800 multicorer. This system is capable of taking eight multicores simultaneously to capture the uppermost sediment surface and sediment-water interface. The device uses transparent plastic tubes that are ~75 cm long with an internal diameter (ID) of 9.5 cm and an outside diameter (OD) of 10.1 cm. The eight tubes are suspended from a frame. The frame makes contact with the seafloor which releases the multicore tubes and is driven by the weight stand into the bottom with hydraulic damping to ensure a slow and controlled entry. Feet swing beneath the multicore tubes to keep the bottom of the tubes supported upon recovery. Up to two GoPro cameras were attached to the MC-800 on each deployment and were used to assess the composition of the seafloor and the quality of the cores recovered. Core recovery was measured on recovery to the fan tail. The tubes were considered consumables and anywhere between one to five (typically three) multicores were cut to length, capped and archived as whole rounds. The remaining multicores were sampled on ship with the upper few centimeters extruded and sampled in 1 cm intervals and deeper sediments sampled at 5 cm intervals. One multicore was typically reserved for pore water samples using Rhizon samplers.

The MC-800 multicore system used during AR76-01 after a successful deployment. Calm seas often led to pristine sediment water interfaces, as pictured here, which could be assessed by the clarity of the water above the sediment and also videos from the GoPro cameras that were mounted on the MC-800 frame. Photo credit: R.V. Kelleher.

Armstrong Gravity Cores (GC)

The main gravity coring system used was the Armstrong gravity corer, often also referred to in written notes as the “WHOI GC”. This device uses commercially available PVC pipe as a core barrel with an ID of 10.7 cm and an OD of 11.4 cm. The pipe was marked with a continuous paleomagnetic line (‘mag line’) along the length of the archive halves, so that when split, the split face of all sections can be oriented relative to each other. A core cutter and core catcher are attached at the bottom of the pipe; the top of the pipe is twice drilled through with a 1/2-inch drill bit and connected to the weight stand using two pin. The weight stand and pipe weighs approximately 800 lb. The system was typically rigged with 15 ft (~4.5 m) or 20 ft (~6 m) sections of pipe, but 10 ft (~3 m) sections were also used. The corer was deployed from the starboard side LARS (Launch And Recovery System) on the Armstrong using 3/8-inch diameter steel wire. Winch speed for lowering in the water was typically around 60 m/min, near bottom contact speed increased and most hits were made around 120 m/min, although sometimes this speed was reduced to limit over penetration in soft sediments. The Armstrong gravity core was landed vertical or near vertical on deck and secured in an upright position to preserve the uppermost sediments before being cut to length, capped, and lowered to horizontal. Each recovered core was cut into ~150 cm (or shorter) sections and capped with plastic end caps held in place with electrical tape.

The RV Armstrong's gravity core top (yellow/brown), weight stand (red), and pipe (white) being deployed over the starboard rail. The pipe was rigged with either a 10, 15, or 20 ft length of 4 inch PVC pipe during AR76-01. One of the main advantages of this coring device is that it can be landed vertically on the ship, thus allowing the scientists to cut the core to length and cap it before lowering it through to horizontal on the deck. This helps minimize deformation to the scientists' precious core top and, as a result, this type of coring was paired with every jumbo piston core and gravity core heavy deployment. Photo Credits: R.G. Hatfield and J.S. Stoner.

Jumbo Piston Cores (JC)

We used the WHOI jumbo piston corer which has a 5000 lb weight. The corer uses high-grade 5.25-inch steel pipe in 10ft (~3 m) sections and can be rigged up to 70 ft (~21 m—the maximum length is controlled by the length of the R/V Armstrong starboard rail). The core liner used in the piston core is the same liner used for the gravity corer and was pre-labeled using the same approach with a continuous paleomagnetic line ('mag line'). The piston corer was rigged with a 9-10 ft (~3 m) trigger core. Both the piston core and trigger core used core catchers. The piston corer was loaded and landed along the starboard rail but was deployed from the A-frame on the stern off the fan tail using the 5/8-inch trawl wire after a load transfer from the ship's crane. Winch speed for the piston corer was typically 60 m/min from the surface and bottom hits were made at 30 m/min to 60 m/min. Each recovered core was cut into ~150 cm (or shorter) sections and capped with plastic end caps help in place with electrical tape.

The jumbo piston core was prepared and recovered in a horizontal position along the starboard rail, but deployed using the 9/16 trawl wire from the stern A-frame. The piston core was transferred from a starboard bucket that held the 5,000 lb weight to a bucket on the stern before deployment using the ship's crane, with the device kept underwater to minimize risk. Many days of AR76-01 were like that pictured here—so calm that these transfers were easy. Photo credit: R.V. Kelleher.

Gravity Core Heavy (GC_h)

In several locations we deployed the WHOI jumbo piston corer without a piston as a gravity corer. Referred to as “the gravity core heavy,” this gravity core set-up was typically rigged at 30 ft in length and used the steel pipes from the piston corer to encase the liner. This configuration gave us the option to leverage the 5000 lb piston core weight to take longer cores than possible than the Armstrong gravity corer system and to have controlled seafloor hits at a set, typically 60 m/min, winch speed (versus the freefall of the jumbo piston core). It was deployed in situations when sediments were complex or had a hard CHIRP reflection and a jumbo piston core would have risked being damaged or getting stuck. The gravity core heavy used the same core cutter and catcher as the piston core and was deployed from the a-frame on the trawl wire, but was built and landed on the rail. Core tops of the gravity core heavy were often suspected to be disturbed, as the set-up did not have a flapper valve and the core was placed horizontal immediately after recovery before the core liner was extruded from the steel pipe. Each recovered core was cut into ~150 cm (or shorter) sections and capped with plastic end caps that are held in place with electrical tape.

The “gravity core heavy” was typically rigged to 30ft in length and used the solid 5,000 lb piston core weight and steel pipes, but was used without a piston and hit the seafloor at the speed of the winch. Sometimes, the right tool for the job is just something heavy. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

Underway Core Processing and Curation

CT Scans

Computed Tomographic (CT) imagery and radiographs were created for all whole-round sediment cores on the Geotek Vertical X-ray CT (VXCT) system with Geotek XCT 6.0 software prior to being processed. The VXCT system uses a 65-watt Thermo Scientific PSX10 Microfocus X-Ray source that is hardened with a 0.25 mm copper filter for Multicores and a 0.75 mm copper filter for Trigger, Jumbo Piston, and Gravity cores. All scans were made with the system voltage set to 130 kV, a binning mode of 4x4 pixels, frame rate of 10 1/s, and an averaging value of 3. Jumbo Piston, Trigger and Gravity cores were scanned with a current of 475 μA , Source-Object Distance (SOD) of 306 cm, and a Source-Detector Distance (SDD) of 559 cm. Multicores were scanned with a current of 210 μA , SOD of 266 mm, and SDD of 519 mm to account for the smaller core diameter. Due to technical issues, the SDD and current were slightly altered for some scans to account for unexplained increases in measured intensity, this resulted in a minor variation in imagery resolution, however peak intensity values were kept between 50-55,000 W/m^2 for all scans while other variables were altered to keep the image quality as consistent as possible. The final resolution and scan configurations are recorded in the .xml metadata file included with the data output folder for each scan.

Radiographs were taken at 0 and 90 degrees for all Trigger, Piston, and Gravity cores (with laminography preserved), and at 0 degrees for Multicores. 0 degrees is relative to the 'mag line' facing the detector. Each of these images had a scan interval of 5 pixels, a scan height of 50 pixels. Helical CT scans were made for all cores with an angular step of 0.3° and included no frame averaging or pitch oversampling. Resulting raw CT data were reconstructed using the proprietary Geotek Image Reconstructor software. Polynomial corrections for cupping were applied based on thickness and density of the material, a standard smoothing filter was applied consistently for all scans, and the Geotek Auto Align function was used to correct for non-linear sections of core. All processing parameters are saved in the .xml metadata file in the reconstructions output folder. These reconstructions were then processed in Geotek CT QuickView with slices made at approximately 1 mm/4 pixel sections (precise interval dependent upon resolution of scan) and images of the 90° and 180° orthogonal views were saved for preliminary correlation between core sections.

MST Data

Several non-destructive physical properties measurements were made on whole-round cores using GEOTEK's Multi-Sensor Core Logger (MSCL), including p-wave velocity, electrical resistivity, magnetic susceptibility, and gamma ray attenuation. These data provided initial characterization of recovered whole-round marine sediment cores, highlighting correlative boundaries between cores and general trends. Once per day or per site (whichever came first), p-wave time of travel (TOT) and ambient room temperature were measured and recorded prior to beginning measurements. Electrical resistivity standards (core sections filled with DI water of varying salinities) and a magnetic susceptibility standard were also measured once per day or per site. An aluminum "layer-cake" standard with five known diameters surrounded by DI water was used to calibrate gamma density once per week.

Core sections were run through the MSCL after equilibrating to room temperature (~20°C) over several hours (minimum of 4 hours). The magnetic line of every core section, drawn on prior to cutting the recovered core into sections, was pointed upward to maintain consistent orientation downcore. To track potential drift in measurements, two electrical resistivity standards and the magnetic susceptibility standard were placed before the first core section and after the last core section. Whole-round core sections were measured at 1 cm resolution, counted over 5 seconds for gamma ray counts, averaged over 5 seconds for electrical resistivity, and 1 second for magnetic susceptibility. Gamma ray attenuation was collected by firing a narrow, focused beam from a ¹³⁷Cs source through the whole-round core section to a detector, where the amount of radiation attenuated is related to the density of the sediment sample. The section then passed through the p-wave rollers, where a p-wave pulse was propagated through the sample and detected by the receiver. Time of travel for the p-wave is also related to the density of the sample, along with its rigidity and incompressibility. Non-contact resistivity was then measured by inducing a small magnetic field to generate electrical currents in the sediment sample that are inversely related to resistivity. Lastly, the core section passed through the 4" Bartington magnetic susceptibility loop sensor (MS2C), where the response of the sample to a small magnetic field was measured.

Following MSCL measurements, data were processed in GEOTEK's MSCL 7.9 program. Measurements of the gamma density and electrical resistivity standards, TOT, and ambient temperature were used to develop calibrations applied in data processing. The relevant core thickness was accounted for as 0.68 cm liner for multicores (MC) and 1.13 cm liner for gravity, trigger, and jumbo piston cores (GC/TC/JC). Magnetic susceptibility was not mass-corrected and instead represents volumetric magnetic

susceptibility. Gamma ray attenuation was converted to bulk density using the measurements of known standards and the GEOTEK calibration file provided for this system.

Splitting

A subset of cores were split in half in the hanger using the OSU-MGR splitter saw which is a circular saw mounted on rails that runs a straight line down the central axis of the core. The blade is set at a height to cut through the liner, but not penetrate the mud underneath. Cores are cut once from the top to the bottom, perpendicular to the mag line (i.e. the mag line is not the cut line), the core is rotated through 180 degrees and then cut a second time. A shop vac was used during and following cutting to prevent plastic waste blowing overboard. The end caps were cut with a carpet knife and a wire on a frame was pulled through the cuts to cut the cores into two halves from base to top. Cores were then lifted from each end and dropped under control to separate the two halves before being carried into the lab for description.

Some of the sediment cores were very wet, which can result in splatter when splitting, as demonstrated by Erin Gregory splitting Section 1 of this core.

Core Description

Each half-round core was placed on a raised wooden rack and cleaned using an 8 cm x 5 cm white, plastic card. Cleaning was performed by lightly scraping the disturbed surface sediment off the core to expose the undisturbed sediment below. White plastic buttons for denoting depth were placed along

the edge of the split core sections at 10 cm depth intervals with numeric labels written in permanent marker every 50 cm. Once cleaned and buttoned, cores were moved to the GEOTEK XZ imaging track (see section below). Core descriptions were written on a standard coring description sheet created by the OSU-MGR. Descriptions highlighted coring disturbances, distinct lithologic contacts, unit colors, grain size and shape, lithologic structure, biogenic composition, and lithogenic composition (see extended methods in Appendix 1). Small samples (using a toothpick or small spatula) were taken from the core to make smear slides to better describe the aforementioned features, when needed. Additional small fractions of mud from each lithology were sieved at $>63 \mu\text{m}$ and viewed under a microscope for preliminary identification of foraminifera fauna and potential intervals for radiocarbon dating. Large rocks that prevented D-tube archival were removed from cores, washed with water, bagged, and placed at the end of the D-tube (tube for storing half-round sediment cores). Significant holes in the cores were filled with cut pieces of foam. After describing the cores, the core liner was cleaned and labeled with printed stickers including the standard core name and QR code linking to core metadata. Cores were covered in plastic wrap, secured at each end with masking tape, and stored in clean D-tubes. Stickers were placed both on the lid and side of the D-tube, and D-tube lids were wrapped in electrical tape. Lastly, fully enclosed cores were stored on a metal rack in the main lab and routinely transferred to the refrigerated van on the fan tail. For additional information please refer to the extended methods in Appendix 1.

Once cores were split, they were brought into the main lab, placed on the description table, cleaned, “buttoned,” and described. There was often much ooo-ing and ahh-ing over the pretty laminations, clasts, and blebs. Photo credit: T.R. Vonnahme.

Imaging

Linescan images were collected using an automated GEOTEK XZ track equipped with light and camera and processed using GEOTEK software. Each core section was measured with an additional 4-inch gray plate at the end of the section to be used as a calibration standard. Color data were extracted from select images through extracting the red, green and blue channels and the total intensity. All sediment values were normalized by the median values for the gray plate standard in each run to correct for any variations between runs. Red, green, and blue channel data were also normalized by the total intensity. Data are reported in 0.25 cm binned intervals, where the total intensity (lightness), red, green, and blue values are calculated from the median of all pixels in that range. Images were cropped to remove any regions near the end caps or sides of the core that may not be representative of the sediment. Depth is relative to the first pixel of the linescan image (0 cm section depth) and the cumulative depth was calculated by adding the section offsets reported from the multisensory track.

Cruise Name, Curation, and Station Numbers

The R/V *Neil Armstrong* assigned name for the cruise was AR76-01. However, samples taken during AR76-01 were given the prefix, AR2307. This sample prefix follows the OSU-MGR nomenclature whereby the first two letters denote the vessel (AR – Neil Armstrong), the first two numbers denote the year of the cruise (23 = 2023), and the final two numbers relate to the month the cruise left port (07 = July). UNOLS, WHOI, and data repositories may refer to datasets and cruise information using the AR76-01 identifier.

Each over-the-side wire operation, successful or not, was given a sequential number and a two letter identifier. Two letter identifiers used during AR76-01 include: PP – Phytoplankton Tow; ZP – Zooplankton Tow; HC – Hydrocast (CTD cast and niskin water bottle collection from the CTD deployment); MC – Multicore; GC – Gravity Core; TC – Trigger Core; JC – Jumbo Piston Core. The same physical location can have several different deployment numbers. For example, a location that had two plankton tows to different depths (i.e., 300 and 60 m), a failed CTD cast, a successful CTD cast, a gravity core, and a piston/trigger core would use six sequential numbers but have nine identifiers (e.g. AR2307 - 1PP, -1ZP, -2PP, -2ZP, -3HC, -4HC, -5GC, -6TC, -6JC). The phytoplankton net and the zooplankton net have the same deployment number as they were deployed during the same over-the-side wire operation. Similarly, the trigger core and the piston core share the same deployment number. The failed CTD has a number, although there are no samples associated with it. Plankton and water samples follow the naming schema outlined in Appendix 1. Information on each deployment was recorded on paper datasheets and in the R2R repository 'elog.'

Several deployments are often grouped together within a location called a station. A station can have one deployment or several different deployments. A new station is assigned when the ship moves a significant enough distance that a different geomorphic target or question was being addressed. For example, Stations 2 and 3 were both on Sukkertop Bank, 11 nmi apart; Station 2 attempted to core an inter moraine complex on the shelf, Station 3 tried to access a sediment package in deeper water. Station numbers were assigned after the operations were complete and are most accurately documented in this report. During operations, only descriptive station names were recorded on paper datasheets or in the 'elog.'

All cores went through the workflow outlined in this document before being labelled with unique identifiers (including QR-coded metadata) following the OSU-MGR schema. Cores were archived in the

refrigerated van on the main deck and shipped back to the OSU-MGR from Reykjavik, Iceland, after the deadhead transit (AR76-02) from Nuuk to Reykjavik. Cores were ingested in the repository and remain in refrigerated storage for later sampling or analysis. While CT and MST data were collected on all archived MC, GC, TC, and JCs, cores that were not split at sea are planned to be split, described and imaged at the OSU-MGR. Meta data was uploaded to the OSU-MGR website (<https://osu-mgr.org/>) along with the NOAA funded IMLGS website (<https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/curator/>) and the NSF funded Arctic Data Center (<https://arcticdata.io/>).

Multibeam bathymetry data and chirp seismic reflection data will be entered into the Rolling Deck to Repository system and archived at NOAA's National Centers Environmental Information (NCEI). These datasets will be linked to a submission at the Arctic Data Center with appropriate metadata (dates collected, collection settings, scientific party, vessel, survey location, funding agency, project award, any processing steps, data quality, etc.) for archival and public access, along with contact information for the PI's. Chirp data will be submitted in standard SEG-Y format and multibeam data in .all format.

Safety is a paramount concern when operating in high-latitude environments. For those on the science party who hadn't previously had to put on a survival suit then the first safety drill soon after leaving port provided that opportunity. Here, Lindsey Monito, Paloma Olarte, Katherine (Katie) Stelling, and Megan Siragusa are flawlessly demonstrating the art of donning a survival suit. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield.

Operation Summaries

Daily Operations Summary Table

Date	Location	Activity	PP/ZP Tow	CTD	MC	GC	TC/JC	3.5 kHz	Multibeam
7/11/2023	In Port, Woods Hole MA	Leave Port, Woods Hole, MA						On	On
7/12/2023	New England/Labrador Shelf	Transit						On	On
7/13/2023	New England/Labrador Shelf	Transit						On	On
7/14/2023	New England/Labrador Shelf	Transit						On	On
7/15/2023	New England/Labrador Shelf	Transit						On	On
7/16/2023	Labrador Sea	Transit						On	On
7/17/2023	Labrador Sea	Transit/Begin Survey						On/Survey	On/Survey
7/18/2023	Labrador Sea	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	1, 2	3, 6, 7	5	4	8	Survey	Survey
7/19/2023	Labrador Sea	End Survey/ Transit						Survey/On	Survey/On
7/20/2023	Labrador Sea/ Davis Strait	Transit						On	On
7/21/2023	Sukkertop TMF	Transit/Begin Survey	11, 12			9, 10		Survey/On	Survey/On
7/22/2023	Sukkertop TMF & Holsteinsborg Trough	Over Side Operations/Survey		13	15	14, 16, 17, 18		Survey/On	Survey/On
7/23/2023	Holsteinsborg Dyb	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey				19, 20	21	Survey/On	Survey/On
7/24/2023	West Greenland Shelf	Transit						On	On
7/25/2023	West Greenland Shelf	Transit/Survey/Over Side Operations				22, 23		Survey/On	Survey/On
7/26/2023	Melville Bugt TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	26, 27	25	29	24, 28		Survey/On	Survey/On
7/27/2023	Melville Bugt TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	34, 35	32		30, 31, 33		Survey/On	Survey/On
7/28/2023	Melville Bugt TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey			36		37, 38	Survey/On	Survey/On
7/29/2023	Melville Bugt TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Transit			39			Survey/On	Survey/On
7/30/2023	Upernavik TMF	Transit/Survey						Survey/On	Survey/On
7/31/2023	Upernavik TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations	40, 41	42		43	44	Survey/On	Survey/On

8/1/2023	Upernavik TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey			45	46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52,		Survey/On	Survey/On
8/2/2023	Upernavik TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	54, 55	56	58	57	53	Survey/On	Survey/On
8/3/2023	Uummannaq TMF	Transit/Survey						Survey/On	Survey/On
8/4/2023	Uummannaq TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	59, 60	61	64	62, 65, 66	63	Survey/On	Survey/On
8/5/2023	Uummannaq TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	67, 68	69	72	70, 73, 74	71	Survey/On	Survey/On
8/6/2023	Uummannaq TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey				75	76	Survey/On	Survey/On
8/7/2023	Uummannaq Trough	Survey/Over Side Operations/Transit				77, 78, 79, 80		Survey/On	Survey/On
8/8/2023	Disko TMF	Transit/Survey/Over Side Operations	81, 82	83	86	84, 87, 88	85, 89	Survey/On	Survey/On
8/9/2023	Disko TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey	90, 91	92	96	93, 94, 95,97, 98		Survey/On	Survey/On
8/10/2023	Disko TMF	Survey/Over Side Operations/Survey				100	99, 101	Survey/On	Survey/On
8/11/2023	Disko TMF	Transit/Survey/Transit						Survey/On	Survey/On
8/12/2023	Davis Strait	Transit						On/Off	On/Off
8/13/2023	Nuuk Fjord System, In Port, Nuuk Greenland	Over Side Operations/In Port		102, 103, 104, 105, 106, 107, 108, 109				On/Off	On/Off

Table 2: Summary of daily operations during BADEX. For the activities listed, transit refers to travel at an unrestricted ship speed (usually 10-11 kt), survey refers to purposefully slower ship speeds (usually 6 kt) to improve the quality of the geophysical data, and over side operations refers to periods when the ship was holding station when sampling was occurring. Deployment numbers are assigned to their operation type i.e. PP/ZP, CTD, MC, GC, TC/JC. In this table, “GC” encompasses both the Armstrong gravity core and the gravity core heavy. The 3.5 kHz (CHIRP) and Multibeam systems were either turned off (Off), operated at survey speed (Survey), or turned on (On), the latter was assigned to data that was collected not at survey speeds (either unrestricted transit speed or on station).

Deployment Summary Table:

Region	Stn. #	Dply. #	Type	Latitude (dec. deg.)	Longitude (dec. deg.)	Depth (m)	Recovery	Split at Sea (Yes/No)	Comments
Harrison Spur	1	1	PP/ZP	55.504707	-56.093442	1248	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Harrison Spur	1	2	PP/ZP	55.501861	-56.084080	1299	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.
Harrison Spur	1	3	CTD	55.501414	-56.082647	1341	-	-	Cast terminated early.
Harrison Spur	1	4	GC	55.505328	-56.096789	1245	3.50 m	Y	USBL. Mud ~0.5 m from weights
Harrison Spur	1	5	MC	55.505806	-56.096465	1247	0.23 – 0.36 m	N	All eight tubes recovered sediment.
Harrison Spur	1	6	CTD	55.511361	-56.092103	1289	-	-	Cast terminated early.
Harrison Spur	1	7	CTD	55.507420	-56.074921	1414	21 bottles	-	-
Harrison Spur	1	8	JC (TC)	55.505914	-56.096672	1250	9.25 m (0 m)	Y (-)	Trigger core lost. Mud on bomb.
Sukkertop Bank	2	9	GC	65.087934	-54.617420	158	0 m	-	Core liner sheared from pipe.
Sukkertop Bank	2	10	GC	65.087931	-54.617439	157	0 m	-	Core liner returned empty.
Sukkertop Bank	3	11	PP/ZP	65.039464	-55.039890	651	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Sukkertop Bank	3	12	PP/ZP	65.039472	-55.039882	651	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.
Sukkertop Bank	3	13	CTD	65.039472	-55.039905	651	21 bottles	-	-
Sukkertop Bank	3	14	GC	65.039377	-55.039263	650	0 m	-	Core liner returned empty.
Sukkertop Bank	3	15	MC	65.039389	-55.039258	650	0.09 – 0.10 m	N	Two of four cores successful.
Holsteinsborg Trough	4	16	GC	66.132275	-55.376673	239	0 m	-	Core liner returned empty.
Holsteinsborg Trough	4	17	GC	66.132278	-55.376680	239	0 m	-	Core liner returned empty.
Holsteinsborg Trough	4	18	GC	66.131958	-55.377523	239	0 m	-	Core liner returned empty.

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Holsteinsborg Trough	5	19	GC	66.497462	-54.493769	405	0m	-	Sediments sampled but washed out.
Holsteinsborg Trough	5	20	GC	66.497471	-54.493779	405	2.22 m	Y	-
Holsteinsborg Trough	5	21	JC (TC)	66.497467	-54.493763	405	0 m (0.71 m)	- (Y)	Piston core sheared at 20 ft.
Kangeruatsiaq Trough	6	22	GC	72.224452	-57.221511	353	3.98 m	Y	Mud on weight stand.
Kangeruatsiaq Trough	6	23	GC _(h)	72.224442	-57.221517	353	5.89 m	Y	Mud on bomb.
Melville Bugt	7	24	GC	74.413451	-64.034748	839	0.99 m	Y	Mud fell out of cutter and catcher.
Melville Bugt	7	25	CTD	74.418824	-64.039455	842	21 bottles	-	-
Melville Bugt	7	26	PP/ZP	74.422586	-64.039307	839	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Melville Bugt	7	27	PP/ZP	74.428081	-64.041648	834	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.
Melville Bugt	7	28	GC	74.410119	-64.029770	847	1.66m	Y	Cutter damaged. Sock in CC.
Melville Bugt	7	29	MC	74.415498	-64.028565	842	0.31 – 0.49 m	N	Eight successful. Six of eight kept.
Melville Bugt	8	30	GC	74.444195	-64.803285	1548	3.95 m	Y	Mud on weight stand.
Melville Bugt	8	31	GC _(h)	74.444388	-64.805770	1545	5.54 m	Y	Mud on bomb.
Melville Bugt	9	32	CTD	74.404663	-64.891949	1647	21 bottles	-	-
Melville Bugt	9	33	GC	74.405376	-64.910430	1679	3.75 m	Y	-
Melville Bugt	9	34	PP/ZP	74.404945	-64.929742	1696	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Melville Bugt	9	35	PP/ZP	74.406367	-64.940225	1707	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.
Melville Bugt	9	36	MC	74.404119	-64.892043	1651	0.32 - 0.50 m	N	Seven of eight successful
Melville Bugt	9	37	JC (TC)	74.404621	-64.901848	1665	14.49 m (2.35 m)	Y (Y)	Mud on bomb. Mud on TC weights.
Melville Bugt	9	38	JC (TC)	74.408420	-64.882251	1628	15.58 m (2.09 m)	Y (Y)	Mud below bomb and TC weights.
Melville Bugt	10	39	MC	74.425358	-63.960301	777	0.43 - 0.52 m	N	Towed multicore with Go-Pros.

Upernavik Slope	11	40	PP/ZP	72.851929	-62.300792	1657	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Upernavik Slope	11	41	PP/ZP	72.851937	-62.300798	1639	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.
Upernavik Slope	11	42	CTD	72.851936	-62.300804	1657	21 bottles	-	-
Upernavik Slope	11	43	GC	72.852346	-62.301052	1657	4.03 m	Y	Mud below weights.
Upernavik Slope	11	44	JC (TC)	72.852635	-62.299188	1656	14.49 m (2.76 m)	Y (Y)	Buried TC and JC. TC has re-core.
Upernavik Slope	11	45	MC	72.835992	-62.260042	1630	0.36 – 0.47 m	N	Eight successful.
Upernavik Slope	12	46	GC	72.872533	-61.742764	1197	4.24 m	Y	Mud most of way up pipe.
Upernavik Slope	12	47	GC	72.866684	-61.744105	1182	2.91 m	Y	USBL. Core top was in coupler (bagged).
Upernavik Slope	12	48	GC	72.866842	-61.744136	1182	4.94 m	Y	USBL. Mud below weights.
Upernavik Slope	12	49	GC _(h)	72.872550	-61.742962	1195	6.68 m	N	Mud 5ft below bomb. Very stiff base.
Upernavik Slope	13	50	GC _(h)	72.861532	-62.052311	1489	6.42 m	Y	Mud 5ft below bomb.
Upernavik Slope	13	51	GC	72.861477	-62.052138	1492	4.09 m	N	-
Upernavik Slope	11	52	GC	72.855776	-62.168493	1538	4.25 m	N	Mud to below weight stand.
Upernavik Slope	11	53	JC (TC)	72.855915	-62.169825	1535	15.62 m (2.54 m)	Y (N)	Mud below bomb and on TC weights.
Upernavik Slope	14	54	PP/ZP	72.886092	-61.541376	886	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Upernavik Slope	14	55	PP/ZP	72.886041	-61.539814	882	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.
Upernavik Slope	14	56	CTD	72.889490	-61.537690	878	21 bottles	-	Deployed with MISO camera
Upernavik Slope	14	57	GC	72.895286	-61.538291	865	2.28 m	N	-
Upernavik Slope	14	58	MC	72.901816	-61.545719	867	0.36 – 0.50 m	N	Deployed with Go-Pro. 2 tubes failed.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	59	PP/ZP	71.155268	-61.259703	1598	-	-	Max depth of cast 300 m.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	60	PP/ZP	71.155260	-61.259683	1600	-	-	Max depth of cast 60 m.

Uuummannaq TMF	15	61	CTD	71.155270	-61.259717	1598	21 bottles	-	-
Uuummannaq TMF	15	62	GC	71.155222	-61.260526	1600	4.47 m	N	Core top was in coupler (bagged).
Uuummannaq TMF	15	63	JC (TC)	71.155214	-61.260528	1596	15.39 m	N (-)	Core deformation. No trigger core.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	64	MC	71.155213	-61.260526	1602	0.41 – 0.54 m	N	Three cores disturbed and not kept.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	65	GC	71.150549	-61.166313	1538	5.77 m	N	Mud below weights.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	66	GC _(h)	71.150301	-61.167493	1540	8.06 m	N	Mud below bomb.
Uuummannaq TMF	16	67	PP/ZP	70.937393	-60.444344	784	-	-	-
Uuummannaq TMF	16	68	PP/ZP	70.936741	-60.442870	783	-	-	-
Uuummannaq TMF	16	69	CTD	70.936316	-60.440957	783	21 bottles	-	-
Uuummannaq TMF	16	70	GC	70.935188	-60.442126	782	4.47 m	N	Core top was in coupler (bagged).
Uuummannaq TMF	16	71	JC (TC)	70.938988	-60.437341	782	10.67 m (2.18 m)	Y (Y)	Mud below weights on TC. JC buried.
Uuummannaq TMF	16	72	MC	70.939591	-60.436605	781	0.36 – 0.42 m	N	Eight successful. Seven of eight kept.
Uuummannaq TMF	16	73	GC	70.935961	-60.443528	783	5.81 m	N	-
Uuummannaq TMF	17	74	GC	70.974315	-60.633160	973	5.28 m	Y	Mud to base of weight stand.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	75	GC	71.150628	-61.258026	1598	5.68 m	Y	Mud to base of weight stand.
Uuummannaq TMF	15	76	JC (TC)	71.154915	-61.260611	1600	15.48 m (1.46 m)	N (N)	Mud on bomb. Mud over TC weights.
Uuummannaq Trough	18	77	GC	70.499427	-61.042003	855	2.80 m	N	Mud 2/3 way up pipe. JR175-VC46 locn.
Uuummannaq Trough	19	78	GC _(h)	70.667231	-58.913553	581	4.31 m	N	Mud at bottom of highest pipe.

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Uuummanaq Trough	19	79	GC	70.666289	-58.917955	580	4.44 m	Y	Mud to base of weight stand.
Uuummanaq Trough	19	80	GC _(h)	70.668991	-59.025807	604	5.84 m	N	Mud on top of bomb.
Disko Bugt TMF	20	81	PP/ZP	68.785614	-59.730104	1316	-	-	-
Disko Bugt TMF	20	82	PP/ZP	68.785755	-59.729621	1317	-	-	-
Disko Bugt TMF	20	83	CTD	68.785418	-59.731333	1318	21 bottles	-	-
Disko Bugt TMF	20	84	GC	68.784955	-59.736838	1321	5.92 m	Y	Core top was in coupler (lost).
Disko Bugt TMF	20	85	JC (TC)	68.785333	-59.746403	1328		N (N)	Mud in bomb. Mud over TC weights.
Disko Bugt TMF	20	86	MC	68.786357	-59.735756	1321	0.46 – 0.56 m	N	All eight successful. GREAT videos.
Disko Bugt TMF	20	87	GC	68.786321	-59.734707	1318	5.91 m	N	Core top was in coupler (lost).
Disko Bugt TMF	21	88	GC	68.770480	-59.615220	1172	1.74 m	N	Lost ~3 m on recovery. Rock in catcher.
Disko Bugt TMF	21	89	JC (TC)	68.770337	-59.615786	1178	17.11 m (2.67 m)	N (N)	Mud on TC weights.
Disko Bugt TMF	22	90	PP/ZP	68.882292	-59.255438	693	-	-	-
Disko Bugt TMF	22	91	PP/ZP	68.881971	-59.255255	640	-	-	-
Disko Bugt TMF	22	92	CTD	68.881547	-59.255781	695	21 bottles	-	-
Disko Bugt TMF	22	93	GC	68.879499	-59.257183	696	0 m	N	Core pipe cracked, no mud recovered.
Disko Bugt TMF	22	94	GC	68.879768	-59.259653	696	2.59 m	N	-
Disko Bugt TMF	22	95	GC _(h)	68.879853	-59.260526	697	4.39 m	N	Mud on 2 pipes.
Disko Bugt TMF	22	96	MC	68.879769	-59.260474	697	0.23 – 0.40 m	N	Four tubes deployed, all successful.
Disko Bugt TMF	23	97	GC	68.750284	-59.466447	892	4.06 m	N	-
Disko Bugt TMF	23	98	GC _(h)	68.750285	-59.466404	893	6.08 m	N	Mud on 2 pipes.
Disko Bugt TMF	20	99	JC (TC)	68.784997	-59.744919	1327	19.54 m (2.41 m)	N (N)	Over penetrated. Cracked trigger arm.
Disko Bugt TMF	24	100	GC	68.589786	-60.030165	1403	5.82 m	N	Core top was in coupler (lost).
Disko Bugt TMF	24	101	JC (TC)	68.597066	-60.029847	1405	16.77 m (2.63 m)	N (N)	Mud in bomb. Mud over TC weights.
Nuup Kangerlua	25	102	CTD	63.950146	-52.370440	245	21 bottles	-	-
Nuup Kangerlua	26	103	CTD	64.080484	-52.069833	398	21 bottles	-	-

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Nuup Kangerlua	27	104	CTD	64.179219	-51.758913	90	1 bottle Chl Max	-	-
Nuup Kangerlua	27	105	CTD	64.180995	-51.780283	266	1 bottle Chl Max	-	-
Nuup Kangerlua	27	106	CTD	64.183528	-51.798288	235	1 bottle Chl Max	-	-
Nuup Kangerlua	27	107	CTD	64.186593	-51.811900	216	1 bottle Chl Max	-	-
Nuup Kangerlua	27	108	CTD	64.189139	-51.823456	89	1 bottle Chl Max	-	-
Nuup Kangerlua	27	109	CTD	64.190933	-51.836956	45	1 bottle Chl Max	-	-

Table 3: Region, station, deployment, deployment type, location, water depth, recovery, whether the core was split at sea, and sample notes for all 109 deployments taken from the R/V Neil Armstrong during BADEX. Further information about each deployment can be found in the operational summaries and in Appendixes 2 through 5.

The land of the midnight sun. Sea ice made for calm seas and beautiful lighting, but no sunsets! Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield.

The long transit from Woods Hole, MA to the Labrador Sea provided ample opportunity for the science party to get acquainted with the process of building core liners for the cruise. Here, Paloma Olarte is demonstrating proficiency in building the upper section of the trigger core for what will become AR2307-7TC which was ultimately returned to the ocean during coring operations at Harrison Spur. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

Labrador Sea (Station 1)

Previous coring in the Cartwright Saddle has produced detailed event layer stratigraphies related to Laurentide ice sheet collapse (Jennings et al., 2015) with lithologies generally suitable for paleomagnetism and microfossil abundances permitting radiocarbon dating. A spur extends from the Cartwright Saddle shelf break with Hamilton Bank at ~1000 mwd, NE into the Labrador Sea, and meets the lower slope around 2500 mwd. Previous coring on the upper part of the spur has yielded sediments with expanded deglacial sections between Heinrich Events 1 and 2 (Tripsanas and Piper, 2008). The combination of expanded LGM lithogenic sediment sections coupled with a Husdon Strait event layer stratigraphy, provided an attractive target to be able to develop into a paleomagnetic and chronostratigraphic framework to import into Baffin Bay. The site also presents an opportunity to track the destabilization and collapse of the Laurentide ice sheet since late MIS3. We occupied one station in this region.

Figure 3. Regional map of Station 1 operations in the Labrador Sea. Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. Multibeam depths are overlaid on the background bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Summary

The vessel slowed to 6 kts at the start of the survey in the Labrador Sea at 1:15 UTC on July 18, 2023. The Knudsen chirp 3260 and Kongsberg EM122 were both used. The EM122 was collected with a 65/65 degree range which resulted in outer edge artifacts (flappy beams). The Kongsberg EM710 was on for part of the survey, but the data quality was limited due to the deeper water depth. That data was not used for analysis. Three XBTs were collected during the survey to capture the temperature variation along the slope. About 55 nmi of data were collected prior to the sampling station. The last two lines before over the side operations began had to be altered to avoid an iceberg flowing across the planned lines.

The survey was designed with crossing lines over a series of cores that had been previously collected along a bathymetric ridge. The first crossing line in deeper water was planned over Vema 16-231 (55.8 N, 56W, 2452 m), a second crossing line was planned above HU2003-047-001PC (55.506 N, 56.093 W, 1264 m) which contained an expanded deglacial record. No high-resolution bathymetry was available for the region; the best data for survey planning came from Office of Canadian Fisheries and Oceans charts. Based on the multibeam data we collected, the bathymetric high is part of a slide complex on the slope. The block with the main coring target on it was partially protected from upslope sediment by a larger high, likely allowing for the preservation of the expanded deglacial record.

A large “Smart Screen” in the main lab was connected to our cruise working geographic information system (GIS), which included legacy data and live read outs of the ships position. This system was very helpful for discussing strategy and planning surveys. Here we are using Office of Canadian Fisheries and Oceans charts, which had the most useful data for planning our Labrador Sea survey. Photo credit: K. Stelling.

The majority of the chirp data along the survey of the lower slope showed a single hard bottom reflector and did not appear to be good coring targets for hemipelagic sediments. On the upper slope we did identify a sequence (station 1, lat, long, water depth) on a bathymetric high where core HU2003-047-001PC was taken. We identified a coring location 0.14 nmi to the northwest of the crossing line, high up the slope where the sequence looked expanded in the chirp.

Station 1 Operations (AR2307-1PP/ZP through AR2307-8JC)

The sea state was very calm throughout the day, however visibility was low due to fog on the water. The major challenge was a 0.7 – 1.5 knot surface current flowing from the NW to the SE; this made it difficult to hold station with Dynamic Positioning (DP) during some operations and meant others had to be sampled while drifting to prevent the instrument or coring device kiting in the current.

The LARS crane used for gravity core deployment was rigged with a frame to carry the phytoplankton and zooplankton nets. We drifted down current with the nets to prevent line kiting. Deployment AR2307-1PP and -1ZP went down to 300 mwd at 20 m/min and returned to the surface at 10 m/min. Samples were collected and AR2307-2PP and 2ZP was deployed to 60 m depth using the same winch speeds as for the 300 m vertical tow. We did not move upstream between the deployments. The ship was repositioned back to the location of AR2307-1 to deploy the CTD (AR2307-3HC). Around 200 mwd on the downcast the CTD software started logging module errors and the oxygen and salinity sensors began reporting unrealistic values. The CTD cast was terminated and returned to the surface to assess the source of these errors (presumed to be sensor cables) on the deck.

A 15 ft gravity core was rigged (AR2307-4GC) with a USBL beacon positioned 30 m above the shackle and the ship was positioned 0.25 nm up current of the intended core site in 1348 mwd in order to drift onto the site to deploy the GC. The core barrel was lowered to 1000 mwd and the bridge controlled the drift to the site and deployed the gravity core. The corer hit the seafloor at a winch speed of 128 m/min and had 2200 lbs of tension on pullout. AR2307-4GC recovered 350.1 cm of sediments.

Multicore AR2307-5MC was deployed with 8 tubes and a Go-Pro camera. The MC hit the seafloor at 40 m/min and collected sediment in all 8 multicore tubes ranging in depth from 21 – 36 cm. MC2 had a severely disturbed surface, so was not retained. Three tubes were archived (MC1, MC5, MC6) and four tubes were sampled at sea for porewater using rhizons (MC4), biomarkers and foraminifera (MC7), and phytoplankton (MC3), and neodymium (MC8); the remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals.

The ship was moved 0.4 nm NNE of the core site for deployment of the CTD, away from the sediment plumes generated by coring operations. The CTD was deployed while drifting with the surface current to prevent instrument kiting. Soon after deployment the CTD again began picking up module errors on the data. AR2307-6HC was terminated about 50 m into the downcast. We suspected communications from the MISO camera were the source of the errors so the downcast of AR2307-7HC was deployed with the MISO camera communication disconnected (no module errors were encountered). Communications were reconnected at max depth to record seafloor images. For the upcast, the MISO camera communications caused interference with the firing of bottle 1. Communications were disconnected and the software was restated to allow bottle 1 to be refired, resulting in the downcast and upcast data being recorded in different files. All 21 bottles fired successfully on the upcast and no further module errors were recorded.

During the upcast of AR2307-7HC, 21 Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths near the bottom, at 1000, 800, 600, 300, 200, 100, 80, 50, 40, 30, 20, at the Chlorophyll maximum at 37, and at 10, 5, and 1 m. Actual depths provided by the CTD depth measurement, less 1 m to correct for the offset between the Niskin bottles and the sensors, are in the tables. The Chlorophyll maximum was detected

near 40 m on the downcast, but was near 35 m on the upcast and therefore not sampled with the Niskin bottle.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients, chlorinity, stable and radiogenic isotopes, and biomarkers. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (Microscopy), Chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the Chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and nutrient enrichment experiments in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations. Additional DNA metabarcoding samples were taken at 200 m.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phyto-plankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary product.	Resp.
24	1	3.5	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	9	X	X	X			X	TRV
22	10	12.8	X	X				X	TRV
21	20	22.8	X	X	X			X	TRV
20	30	32.8	X	X				X	TRV
18	37 CM	40.1	X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
17	50	52.8	X	X				X	TRV
13	80	82.9							TRV
10	100	103.2	X	X					TRV
9	200	204.3		X		X			TRV
5	300	305.3		X					TRV
4	600	607.1		X					TRV
3	800	808.9		X					TRV
2	1000	1011.2		X					TRV
1	1383	1399.4		X					TRV

Table 4: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-07HC. CM = Chlorophyll Max.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.5		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	9	X	X	X	X	ACM
22	10	12.8		X	X	X	ACM
21	20	22.8		X	X	X	ACM
20	30	32.8		X	X	X	ACM
18	37	40.1		X	X	X	ACM
17	50	52.8	X	X	X	X	ACM
13	80	82.9		X	X	X	ACM
10	100	103.2	X	X	X	X	ACM
9	200	204.3		X	X	X	ACM
5	300	305.3		X	X	X	ACM
4	600	607.1		X	X	X	ACM
3	800	808.9		X	X	X	ACM
2	1000	1011.2	X	X	X	X	ACM
1	1383	1399.4	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 5: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-07HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
24	1	3.5		X
19	40	39.8	X	
18	40	40.1	X	
13	80	82.9	X	
12	80	83.0	X	
11	80	83.1	X	
9	200	204.3	X	
8	200	203.9	X	
7	200	204.1	X	
6	260	264.5		X
5	300	305.3		X
4	600	607.1		X
3	800	808.9		X
2	1000	1011.2		X
1	1383	1399.4		X

Table 6: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-07HC.

Following the successful deployment of AR2307-7HC we concluded not to run the MISO camera with active communication on the downcast or upcast during CTD deployment unless the problem could be solved by the marine technicians and SSSGs.

The ship was repositioned back to the primary coring site to deploy a 40 ft jumbo piston core and 10 ft trigger core. DP held us in place during operations. The core barrel was held briefly above the target at 1100 mwd before being deployed at 40 m/min to the seafloor. Pull out tensions on AR2307-8TC/JC were 16,500 lb and both the trigger core weight stand and the piston core bomb returned with mud on them. The piston core cutter returned damaged suggesting it took a hard impact on deployment. The piston core was cut into 7 sections and 9.25 m of sediments were recovered. The trigger core was recovered to the ship but was lost to the ocean from the fantail during separation of the core liner from the weight stand. The deck was washed down, and coring gear was secured for transit.

For summaries of the preliminary results from the CTD and underway data from Station 1, please refer to the information in Appendix 2. For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core description summaries associated with Station 1 operations, please refer to the images and information in Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

Following completion of over the side operations at station 1, about 32 nmi of multibeam and chirp data were collected at 6 kts between 2:08 and 7:10 UTC on July, 19, 2023. This was to fill in the multibeam data around features of interest. One XBT was conducted at the beginning of the survey. After completion of this survey, the vessel sped up to 10 kt for the transit to Holsteinsborg Dyb.

There was a lot of excitement for the first sediment core, AR2307-4GC, recovered during the expedition. Here, many hands are sectioning the core with blue end caps indicating the top of a section and red end caps indicating the bottom. Photo credit: J. Wade-de Jong.

Sukkertop Bank TMF and Holsteinsborg Dyb TMF (Stations 2 – 5)

Compared to systems further north, relatively little is known about the Sukkertop Bank TMF and Holsteinsborg Dyb TMF systems. Ryan et al. (2016) noted the over deepening in the SW Greenland trough systems resulted from intense glacial erosion during ice streaming, and that the excavated material was deposited on the outer continental shelf. Roberts et al. (2010) suggested that a paleo ice stream, Holsteinsborg Isbrae, occupied Holsteinsborg Dyb Trough, reached the shelf edge on the north side of Davis Strait (Figure 4) and formed the Hellefiske moraines on the shelf and small TMFs.

The Holsteinsborg Dyb and Sukkertop Bank troughs are parallel NE to SW trending systems which meet the shelf break at ~200-300 mwd, presenting a relatively shallow paleo-grounding zone depth for Baffin Bay. Thick Holocene sediments in the inner troughs suggest rapid sedimentation (Allan et al., 2021; Erbs-Hansen et al., 2013) while sedimentary structures in the multichannel seismic data from Holsteinsborg Dyb are interpreted as possible contourites, associated with interaction with northward flow of the WGC (Erbs-Hansen et al., 2013). Abundant calcareous benthic foraminifers are found in shelf trough cores with assemblages related both to Atlantic Water and glacial meltwater/Polar water entering from the East Greenland Current during the Holocene (Allan et al., 2021; Erbs-Hansen et al., 2013). Study of these systems is important not only to reconstruct ice margin behavior at the southern end of Baffin Bay, but also to characterize the Atlantic Water endmember as it enters Baffin Bay, prior to its northward flow along the Greenland margin (Erbs-Hansen et al., 2013; Seidenkrantz et al., 2019).

Figure 4. Regional map of Stations 2 through 5 operations in the Sukkertop Bank and Holsteinsborg Dyb areas. Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. Background bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Summary

We started a survey of the Sukkertoppen Bank slope at 11:43 UTC on July 21st, 2023 at a speed of around 6 knots. The chirp, and both the EM710 and EM120 multibeam systems were used. The survey went up the slope and crossed an existing seismic line that previous data had indicated contained acoustically laminated sediments. On the outer shelf, we surveyed and identified a series of moraines and attempted to take gravity cores (station 2). We then steamed across the shelf to drive a line down the slope, crossing the package of previously identified laminated sediments from a different angle (station 3). That down-slope survey line was at ~6 kts. About 55 nmi of survey data were collected in this region. Four total XBTs were done in this region. One failed due to a miscommunication. The survey ended at 22:10 UTC on 07/21/2023.

We started a survey of the Holsteinsborg Trough region at 09:23 UTC on July 22nd, 2023. The survey included the chirp and both multibeams. The POS-MV was having problems through much of this survey and was reset at 11:12 UTC. We also explored the chirp settings on the first portion of the shelf where there was a lack of sediment to tune it for this depth. Two XBTs were done for this survey. The survey started on the upper slope and continued along a transect of the shelf. Eventually the EM120 was turned off because the water was too shallow. Partway onto the shelf we identified a bathymetric low between moraines. This location had multiple acoustically stratified layers in the chirp and had low backscatter values, which was in contrast to most of the area we had previously surveyed on the shelf. We surveyed around this region to map two coincident basins and identify gravity coring targets (station 4). Following operations at station 4, we continued a NE survey across the shelf into the deepest basin in the trough. We identified coring targets and collected crossing lines (station 5). After coring, we surveyed more of this basin for a more complete picture of the spatial dynamics. This survey ended at 09:15 UTC on 07/23/2023.

Station 2 Operations (AR2307-09GC through AR2307-10GC).

Station 2 targeted a small moraine complex on the edge of the shelf in ~160 mwd. We positioned the ship to find a small hollow between two bathymetric highs in an attempt to recover ponded sediments from the inter-moraine complex. AR2307-9GC was rigged as a 15 ft gravity core, penetrated the bottom at 120 m/min, and had 800 lb of pull-out tension. The weight stand came back to the surface with no pipe attachment, and we assumed the pipe sheared from the weight stand as it encountered a hard surface during deployment. A second 10ft gravity core (AR2307-10GC) was rigged and deployed in the same location at the same winch speed but returned empty. We concluded that the bottom was too hard to be sampled with a gravity core. We abandoned the station.

Station 3 Operations (AR2307-11PP/ZP through AR2307-15MC)

A patch of faint parallel reflectors was identified beneath a surface hard reflector at 660 mwd. The first two operations at the station were vertical tows for phytoplankton and zooplankton. The two nets were rigged from a frame and first taken down to 300 m at 20 m/min and recovered at 10 m/min while maintaining position on station (AR2307-11PP/ZP). The nets were sampled, rinsed and sent back down to 60 mwd at the same winch speed to recover AR2307-12PP/ZP).

The MISO camera was not deployed with the CTD and the AR2307-13HC was deployed with no major issues. The bottom depth was 651 m and the bottom water was taken near 640 m. All 21 available Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths near the bottom (640 m), at 550, 400, 300, 200, 100, 70, 50, 40, 30, 20, Chlorophyll maximum at 37, 10, 5, and 1 m. Actual depths provided by the CTD depth measurement, less 1 m to correct for the offset between the Niskin bottles and the sensors, are in the tables. The chlorophyll maximum was not very distinct, but a minor peak was detected near 12 m on the downcast. Thus, the 10 m sample was taken as the chlorophyll maximum.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.5	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.5	X	X	X			X	TRV
22	10	12.4	X	X				X	TRV
29	20	22.7	X	X	X			X	TRV
19	30 CM	32.7	X	X				X	TRV
18	37 CM	41.7	X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
17	50	52.3	X	X				X	TRV
12	100	102	X	X					TRV
9	300	302							TRV
7	400	401		?					TRV
3	640	642		X					TRV

Table 7: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-13HC. CM =Chlorophyll Max.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.5		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.5		X	X	X	ACM
22	10	12.4	X	X	X	X	ACM
20	20	22.7		X	X	X	ACM
19	30	32.7		X	X	X	ACM
18	40	41.7	X	X	X	X	ACM
17	50	52.3		X	X	X	ACM
12	100	102	X	X	X	X	ACM
10	200	202	X	X	X	X	ACM
9	300	302	X	X	X	X	ACM
7	400	401		X	X	X	ACM
5	550	551	X	X	X	X	ACM
3	640	642	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 8: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-13HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
21	10	12.4		X
13	70	69.5		X
11	200	202		X
5	300	305.3		X
4	600	607.1		X
3	800	808.9		X
2	1000	1011.2		X
1	1383	1399.4		X

Table 9: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers.

A good yield from a plankton net! Tobias Vonnahme hopes those tiny plants will like some additional nitrate, silicate, or phosphate. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

A 15 ft Armstrong gravity core was deployed (AR2307-14GC), hit the bottom at 120 m/min and had 1,100 lb of pull-out tension. AR2307-14GC returned empty having recovered no sediment presumably due to the hard nature of the seafloor under strong current control. The multicorer was deployed with 4 multicore tubes (AR2307-15MC) and returned with sediment in 2 of the four tubes, each less than 10 cm. MC1 was archived and MC3 was sampled for forams, biomarkers, and neodymium, the remaining sediment was bagged at 5 cm intervals. The Go-Pro camera deployed with the multicore showed sandy and rocky compositions to the seafloor. The station was abandoned thereafter.

Station 4 Operations (AR2307-16GC through AR2307-18GC)

A small depression was identified in the middle reaches of the shelf seaward of the main Holsteinsborg Trough. We deployed a series of three 10 ft gravity cores that aimed to punch through the surface sandy layer to a series of faint reflectors in the sub-surface that might represent a sub-glacial contact facies. The first two gravity cores (AR2307-16GC and AR2307-17GC) were at the same location, the third (AR2307-18GC) was 50 m to the southeast. AR2307-16GC hit the bottom at 120 m/min, AR2307-17GC and AR2307-18GC both hit the bottom at 40 m/min. Pull out tensions were 900 lbs, 925 lbs, and 850 lbs respectively. All three gravity cores returned empty, though AR2307-18GC had a small amount of very fine sand in the core catcher. We concluded the bottom was too hard, sandy, and compacted on the shelf to be sampled with a gravity corer; a vibrocore would have been more ideal in this situation.

Station 5 Operations (AR2307-19GC through AR2307-21TC/JC)

The outer basin of the main Holsteinsborg Dyb Trough was the target of station 5 operations and aimed to date the basal contact associated with glacial retreat of the margin. A small bench was identified above the deepest part of the basin where reflectors lied conformably, and the CHIRP could see 15-20 m into the sediment. AR2307-19GC was rigged as a 15ft gravity core, hit the bottom at 120 m/min, and had 1600 lbs of pull-out tension on the wire. The corer returned to the ship with ~1 m of mud on the outer barrel but the core had washed out on the trip back to the ship as evidenced by sediment in the water. AR2307-20GC was rigged as a 10ft gravity core, hit the bottom at 120 m/min, had 2000 lbs of pull-out tension, and returned with mud almost to the weight stand and recovered 222.1 cm of sediments. AR2307-21TC/JC was rigged to 40ft and deployed from the fan tail at 30 m/min to the seafloor. The hit was hard, swinging the main block, and pull out tension peaked at 16,500 lb. The trigger core recovered 0.71 m of sediments. The piston core pipe sheared at the bolts at the 20ft joint during deployment and two steel barrels did not return to the ship. Coring operations were terminated at station 5 shortly thereafter.

Coupler bolts sheared during the deployment of AR2307-21JC, leading to the loss of the bottom two 10 ft (~3 m) steel pipes, a cracked core pipe, and no sediment recovered. The cracked core liner now sits in Chief Scientist Rob Hatfield's office to keep him humble while making important decisions. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

For summaries of the preliminary results from the CTD and underway data from Station 2 through 5, please refer to the information in Appendix 2. For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core description summaries associated with these four stations, please refer to the images and information in Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

On the morning of July 24th, 2023 we crossed the Arctic Circle at ~66.66 °N and headed north towards Melville Bugt. The further we progressed north, the more icebergs we encountered and the heavier the sea ice became. Here, newly certified bluenoses Robert Kelleher and Shannon Klotsko are attempting to locate any potential ice hazards that might be lurking on the horizon. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

Kangersuatsiaq Basin (Station 6)

Kangersuatsiaq Basin is a small ~300 meter deep shelf depression between the Uummannaq Trough to the south and Upernavik Trough to the north. Cosmogenic nuclide data from the coastline suggests this area was deglaciated around 11.3 ka (Corbett et al., 2013; Sinclair et al., 2016), but no data exist from this area of the shelf between the southern and northern bounding troughs. Two gravity cores in this area were taken from the deepest part of the mid shelf.

Figure 5. Regional map of Station 6 operations in the Kangersuatsiaq Basin. Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. Multibeam depths are overlaid on the background bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Summary

The vessel was steaming at 11 kt on a NW heading collecting Multibeam and CHIRP data on transit to Melville Bugt as we passed over some small basins north of Uummannaq Trough but south of Upernavik Trough. On transit we noted an acoustically transparent layer conformably overlying a strong reflector that varied from a few meters to more than 12 m below the seafloor. The ship was slowed and turned to the south and then to the NE to get a crossing line over the basin. This small survey was conducted at 6 kt. We identified a transparent package approximately 0.125 nmi to the SW of the crossing line where the depth to the strong reflector was about 8 m and began gravity coring operations.

Station 6 Operations (AR2307-22GC through AR2307-23GC)

After difficulty coring at Stations 2-5 due to hard surfaces and difficulty with rigging the WHOI Jumbo Piston Core system for shorter (<40 ft) deployments, we sought a location where we could 'shake-down' a coring device for intermediate length deployments and where hard reflectors might be considered risky for a piston core in freefall. Thus, an additional goal of Station 6 was to test the so-called "gravity core heavy" (see science methods, coring operations) and compare its recovery to the Armstrong gravity core.

AR2307-22GC was deployed as a 15ft Armstrong gravity corer that was lowered at 60 m/min, accelerated to 120 m/min ~100 m above the seafloor, and had 2050 lbs of pull-out tension. On recovery mud was on the weight stand but the top of the pipe drained clean water. This suggested overpenetration of the corer, but compression of the mud as it entered the pipe so that it did not hit the base of the pipe coupler, and that a core top sample might be reasonably well intact. AR2307-22GC recovered 397.9 cm of sediments. AR2307-23GC was deployed as a 30 ft gravity corer heavy using the piston core weights. It went down at 40 m/min until it contacted the seafloor, pull out tensions were 11,500 lbs. AR2307-23GC recovered 589.3 cm of sediment and contained grey clay and large clasts at the base suggesting that we sampled the reflector seen in the CHIRP profile. Operations concluded at station 6 and the ship was secured for transit.

For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core descriptions associated with Station 6 operations, please refer to the images and information in Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

Melville Bugt (Stations 7 – 10)

The Melville TMF is built from 3 cross-shelf troughs (northern, central, and southern troughs) that each contained their own ice streams (Newton et al., 2017; Slabon et al., 2016). We focused on the TMF seaward and northward of the largest central trough that meets the shelf break at ~500-800 m. The southernmost of the three troughs is called Upernavik Trough and was studied in isolation during occupations at stations 11 through 14. A single moraine had been identified on the slope in a single multibeam line at ~800 mwd and ice retreat from the shelf is tentatively inferred to have taken place by 15 ka (Slabon et al., 2016). Within the trough, multiple grounding zone wedges reflect periods of ice stream stabilization and ice shelf fringing (Dowdeswell and Fugelli, 2012), possibly in response to YD cooling (Dowdeswell et al., 2014; Hogan et al., 2016; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2013a; Sheldon et al., 2016). Aside

from the line collected by the Polar Stern (ARK XXV/3) in 2010 as shown in Slabon et al. (2016) and a few exploratory lines driven during MSM44 in 2015, very few geophysical data and no known cores exist from an area we termed the ‘hook’ to the NW corner of Melville Bugt trough. Understanding the glaciological and sedimentological regimes in this area was a focus of the geophysical survey and stations 7 through 10.

Figure 6. Regional map of operations of Stations 7 through 10 in Melville Bugt. Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. Multibeam depths are overlaid on the background bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Summary

At 21:55 UTC on July 25th, 2023, we started our survey on the Melville Bugt Hook, the physiographic feature to the north of the trough mouth fan. We continually operated in this area (survey or over-the-side operations) until we left the region on July 30th, 2023 following the recovery of AR2307-39MC at around 00:30 UTC. The survey was conducted at 6 knots in ice-free conditions and slower if there was ice. The chirp, and at least one of the multibeam systems was run throughout the entire length of the survey. They were also run while doing over-the-side operations for information about changes in depth and stratigraphy.

The initial survey line was designed based on an existing seismic line and to be perpendicular to the contours of the Hook feature. We went down slope first, and then ran a similar line up slope. Additional lines were collected to cross these principal lines, however, a typical surveying grid was not possible to accomplish due to the need to constantly maneuver the ship in heavy sea ice conditions. Several interesting features were noted from the surveys. These include a series of ridges that ran along bathymetric contours at a range of depths, some more prominent than others. There was also more sediment, and that sediment was more coherent, in the southern portion of the hook than on the northern side of the depression. In deep water, canyons and gullies were identified on the slope on the northern side of the study area.

Station 7 Operations (AR2307-24GC through AR2307-29MC)

Station 7 targeted a thin sediment package in the geophysical data that draped the seafloor between two moraine complexes. The sea state was very calm throughout the day; however, visibility was often low due to fog, and we operated very close to a large ice flow. As a result, we drifted around on station at the whim of the ice. AR2307-24GC was rigged as a 10ft WHOI gravity core, hit the bottom at 120 m/min, and had 1900 lbs of pull-out tension. On recovery from the water to the ship sediments fell back through the core catcher and core cutter. AR2307-24GC recovered 0.99 m of sediments in a single section.

The marine technicians and SSSG's had worked closely to resolve the CTD module errors that were attributed to the MISO camera at Station 1. AR2307-25HC was the first time the CTD was operated with a running MISO camera system and the deployment was successful with zero module errors logged during deployment. The ship was not moved significantly for AR2307-25HC following the recovery of gravity core AR2307-24GC. A turbidity peak near the bottom was encountered that raised questions as to the nature of the water column following coring operations. However, a turbidity peak of a comparable magnitude was also found during AR2307-32 HC, when no coring operations took place before the CTD cast. Thus, we suggest that the turbidity peak in AR2307-25HC is likely not related to the coring disturbance, but is a nepheloid layer associated with bottom currents.

AR2307-25HC was successfully deployed with the MISO camera operating and no module errors were observed during deployment. The bottom depth for AR2307-25HC was 848 m (based on the CTD altimeter, contrasting with 842 m multibeam – we consider the CTD altimeter to be more accurate) and the bottom water was taken at 840 m. All 21 available Niskin bottles were triggered near the bottom and above, nominal depths 840 m, 300, 200, 100, 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, Chlorophyll maximum at 21, 10, 5, and 1 m (see table for actual bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a distinct peak at 26 m, but the peak moved to a shallower depth during the upcast and the ChlMax sample was taken from 21 m.

However, later PAM measurements showed that the 10 m samples had higher Chl a fluorescence values than our suspected ChlMax sample (see Appendix 2 for details).

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients, stable isotopes. Samples in the upper 200 m were taken for biomarkers and samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.8	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.6	X	X	X			X	TRV
22	10	12.6	X	X				X	TRV
21	20	22.8	X	X	X			X	TRV
20	21 CM	23.7	X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
17	30	32.5	X	X				X	TRV
13	40	42.9	X	X				X	TRV
9	50	52.5						X	TRV
8	60	62.5	X	X					TRV
7	100	102.3	X	X					TRV
6	200	202.1		X					TRV
2	300	301.8		X					TRV
1	840	839.6		X					TRV

Table 10: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-25HC. CM = Chlorophyll Max.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.8		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.6	X	X	X	X	ACM
22	10	12.6		X	X	X	ACM
21	20	22.8	X	X	X	X	ACM
20	21	23.7		X	X	X	ACM
17	30	32.5		X	X	X	ACM
13	40	42.9		X	X	X	ACM
9	50	52.5	X	X	X	X	ACM
8	60	62.5		X	X	X	ACM
7	100	102.3	X	X	X	X	ACM
6	200	202.1		X	X	X	ACM
2	300	301.8	X	X	X	X	ACM
1	840	839.6	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 11: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-25HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
20	21	23.7	X	
13	40	42.9	X	
6	200	202.1	X	

Table 12: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-25HC.

Over the side operations at Station 7 were conducted in the close vicinity to a large ice floe. Such floes were typical in Melville Bugt TMF region and resulted in more spaghetti-like survey lines than a beautifully mown lawn. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

Plankton tows AR2307-26PP/ZP and AR2307-27PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively following the CTD cast. AR2307-28GC was rigged as a 10ft WHOI gravity core to try and capture the full sediment sequence that was sampled, but lost during recovery of AR2307-24GC. A cotton tube sock was cut and taped in place on the inside of the core catcher in an attempt to restrict fine grained sediment flow back through the aluminum fingers of the core catcher. The core cutter was slightly damaged suggesting it hit something hard, and there was coarse material at the bottom of the core suggesting we sampled the complete sedimentary sequence at Station 7. AR2307-28GC hit the bottom at 120 m/min, had 1700 lbs of pull-out tension, recovered 1.66 m of sediments, had ~67 cm more than AR2307-24GC, and was cut into two sections. Multicore AR2307-29MC was the last deployment at Station 7. All eight multicore tubes returned full with depths ranging from 0.31 to 0.49

cm. Four tubes had well preserved sediment/water interfaces (MC2, MC4, MC5, MC8), two were cloudy (MC1, MC7), and two were very cloudy (MC3, MC6) and not retained. Three tubes were archived (MC1, MC4, MC7), and three tubes were sampled for porewater using rhizons (MC5), biomarkers and foraminifera (MC2), and biology (MC8), the remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals. The deck was secured, and the vessel was prepared for survey.

Station 8 Operations (AR2307-30GC through AR2307-31GC)

Station 8 targeted the transparent unit that had accumulated on a bench at ~1550 mwd at slightly shallower depths on the slope than we investigated later at Station 9. Based on the 'shake-down' results at Station 6, we decided to pair a gravity core heavy to recover a longer sequence with a hard reflector at the base with a shorter Armstrong gravity core to make sure the uppermost sediments had minimal deformation—a coring strategy we adopted for all remaining gravity core heavy targets of the cruise. AR2307-30GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2800 lbs of pull-out tension. The core pipe returned with mud to the top the barrel and mud was visible on the weight stand. AR2307-30GC recovered 3.95 m of sediments and was cut into 3 sections. AR2307-31GC was rigged as a 30 ft gravity core heavy using the piston core weight to sample deeper into the sequence at Station 8. AR2307-31GC hit the bottom at 40 m/min, had 15,600 lbs of pull-out tension, returned with mud on the bomb, and recovered 5.54 m of sediments.

Station 9 Operations (AR2307-32HC through AR2307-38PC)

It was a bright sunny day during the first day of operations at Station 9. Station 9 targeted an acoustically stratified sediment package that was surveyed at deeper water depths, below the bench bedform that confined the transparent unit cored at Station 8. In this location, the Chirp imaged reflectors more than 35 meters below the seafloor. The location we chose for AR2307-32HC through AR2307-37JC along the initial survey line was a trade-off between being distal enough from the bench bedform of Station 8 that we could image deeper reflectors with the CHIRP, but shallow enough where the reflectors had a consistent thickness. AR2307-38JC was cored the following day after an overnight survey and was in slightly shallower water further up the slope, but in an identical acoustic facies and where reflectors could be clearly traced to AR2307-37JC. A full station was implemented at Station 9.

AR2307-32HC was successfully deployed with all 21 bottles firing. The bottom depth was 1647 m, and the bottom water was taken at the deepest point of the CTD cast (1638 m), and just above the turbidity peak (1560 m) to avoid sampling resuspended sediments. The remaining Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths 1200, 900, 700, 420, 360, 300, 200, 100, 70, 50, 40, 30, Chlorophyll maximum at 20, 10, 5, and 1 m (see table for actual bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a distinct peak at ~23 m, with a second deep Chl Maximum at about 30 m. Only the shallower Chl Max was sampled as Chl Max.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.9	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	8.2	X	X	X			X	TRV
21	10	18.7	X	X				X	TRV
20	20 CM	22.9	X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
19	30	29.9	X	X				X	TRV
18	40	42.8	X	X				X	TRV
13	50	52.9	X					X	TRV
11	100	102.7	X	X					TRV
9	200	202.5		X					TRV
8	300	302.5		X					TRV
7	360	362		X					TRV
6	420	421.5		X					TRV
5	700	700.2		X					
4	900	899.7		X					
3	1200	1198.3		X					
2	1560	1558.2		X					
1	1638	1637.4		X					

Table 13: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-32HC. CM = Chlorophyll Max

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.9		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	8.2	X	X	X	X	ACM
21	10	18.7		X	X	X	ACM
20	20 ChlMax	22.9		X	X	X	ACM
19	30	29.9	X	X	X	X	ACM
18	40	42.8		X	X	X	ACM
13	50	52.9		X	X	X	ACM
12	70	73.1	X	X	X	X	ACM
11	100	102.7		X	X	X	ACM
9	200	202.5	X	X	X	X	ACM
8	300	302.5		X	X	X	ACM
7	360	362		X	X	X	ACM
6	420	421.5		X	X	X	ACM
5	700	700.2	X	X	X	X	ACM
4	900	899.7		X	X	X	ACM
3	1200	1198.3		X	X	X	ACM
2	1560	1558.2		X	X	X	ACM
1	1638	1637.4	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 14: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-32HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
21	10	18.7		X
18	40	42.8		X
9	200	202.5		X
7	360	362		X
6	420	421.5		X
4	900	899.7		X
3	1200	1198.3		X
2	1560	1558.2		X
1	1638	1637.4		X

Table 15: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-32HC.

AR2307-33GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2600 lbs of pull-out tension. The weight stand had not been rinsed down since the last deployment, so it was unclear if mud was on the weight stand, but mud was all the way up the pipe. AR2307-33GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 374.5 cm of sediments. Plankton tows AR2307-34PP/ZP and AR2307-35PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively following the gravity core. AR2307-36MC was rigged with 8 multicore tubes but without a Go-Pro camera as the rigging of the system would have held up the deployment in tricky ice covered conditions. Bottom contact was made at 40 m/min. Seven of the eight multicore tubes returned with sediment; MC4 was empty. A living anemone was found in the bottom of MC3 suggesting it had been scooped up by the feet during pull out of the seafloor and raises questions about the stratigraphic nature of the very bottom of multicores taken in soft sediment. Lengths ranged from 0.32 – 0.50 m, three had clear surfaces (MC2, MC3, MC8), two were cloudy (MC1, MC5), and two were very cloudy (MC6, MC7). Following recovery to the ship MC8 was lost on deck. Three tubes were archived (MC1, MC5, MC7), and three were sampled for porewater using rhizons (MC6), biomarkers and foraminifera (MC2), and neodymium (MC3), the remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals.

AR2307-37JC/TC was rigged as a 50 ft piston core with a 10 ft trigger core. It was designed to only have a small amount of freefall during deployment, approximately 5ft, as the last two deployments of the piston corer resulted in the weight being buried in the mud. AR2307-37JC/TC hit the bottom at 60 m/min, and had 17,700 lbs of pull-out tension. Both the trigger core and piston core had mud on their weights and the coring pipe was also caked in clayey mud over an inch thick the entire length of the barrel. AR2307-37TC recovered 235.2 cm of sediments in two sections. AR2307-37JC had sediment all the way up to the piston, recovered 1448.9 cm of sediments, and was cut into 10 sections. The deck was secured, we sat on station for a few hours to allow bridge personnel time to rest from continuously operating in heavy drifting sea ice, and began a survey to fill in the multibeam map of the area.

Before the cores get described from the split surface, our first hint of what we got is the mud on the outside of the pipe. Katie Stelling shows off how clayey the mud was in this Melville Bugt core; cores from this region came up with an inch of mud caked to the outside of the pipe! Erin Gregory poses with some fine-grained grey sediment from the Labrador margin. Photo Credits: B.T. Reilly & K. Stelling.

Towards the end of the survey we headed back to the station to get a crossing line. The cross line at the site of AR2307-37JC/TC showed more variability in unit thickness between reflectors than expected so we chose a site further up the slope for AR2307-38JC/TC. AR2307-38JC/TC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core, 10 ft trigger core, and was given 8-10 ft of free fall. AR2307-37JC/TC hit the bottom at 60 m/min and had 17,300 lb of pull-out tension. Both the trigger core and piston core had mud to below their weights, but not on their weights. AR2307-38TC recovered 209.2 cm of sediments and was cut into two sections. Like AR2307-37JC/TC, the coring pipe of AR2307-38JC was caked in clayey mud over an inch thick the entire length of the barrel. AR2307-38JC recovered 1555.7 cm of sediments and was cut into 11 sections. The upper meter had water on top of the core and two intervals in sections 10 and 11 were sheared apart leaving voids in the sediment. The one in section 11 closed itself as it was loaded vertically in the CT scanner. The interval in section 11 remained visible in the CT image. The deck was secured, and we transited out of the area.

Station 10 Operations (AR2307-39MC)

Station 10 targeted a prominent bathymetric feature that ran along the ~780 m bathymetric contour in the multibeam data. As the nature of the feature was unclear, we mounted two GoPro cameras to the multicore frame and rigged the multicorer with four multicore tubes. In order to see how the nature of the feature evolved we planned to tow the multicorer ~4-5 m above the seafloor for ~0.25 miles along the central axis to the NNW. To monitor the position of the multicorer along the axis and its depth relative to the ship we deployed a USBL at the top of the multicorer and linked the USBL location feed to the Multibeam data previously collected for this feature. We launched an XBT to get an accurate sound profile for the USBL during deployment of the multicorer. The multicorer hit the bottom at 20 m/min. The winch was raised 3 m and we added an extra meter to establish a depth ~4m off the seafloor. We

began the transit at 0.3 kt and increased to 0.5 kt about 10 mins into the transit. Wire was payed out 1m at a time a total of three times to account for kiting of the multicorer and the multibeam seafloor depth increasing as we transited. We towed the multicorer for approximately 30 mins before coming up 15 m on the wire, and then recovering the multicorer to the surface at 40 m/min. AR2307-39MC returned with 4 full multicore tubes with depths ranging from 0.43 – 0.52 m, three had clear sediment water interfaces (MC1, MC4, MC8) and one was cloudy (MC5). The three tubes with clear interfaces were archived. Although the rough bathymetry in this region prevented a clear image of sediments on the seafloor, both the video and recovered multicore sediments demonstrated a muddy sediment drape over the bedform and not a rocky bottom.

For summaries of the preliminary results from the CTD and underway data from Station 7 through 10, please refer to the information in Appendix 2. For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core description summaries associated with these four stations, please refer to the images and information in Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

Rob Hatfield points to the site he wants to core as the team picks the location for Station 9, in deeper water than the cores taken from the 'bench' bed form feature of Station 8. He likes the site! Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly

Core splitting is a key part of core processing and involves the splitting of the whole round core into a working half and an archive half. A black line on the end caps help orient the cores to ensure that they are consistently split relative to each other. Here, Lindsey Monito and Paloma Olarte are slicing the liner; Joe Stoner is keeping a cut core from rolling off the splitting table. Don't cut on the mag line! Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield.

Upernavik TMF (Stations 11 – 14)

Upernavik TMF is the first trough south of the extensive Melville trough that sits at the northern end of the west Greenland margin (Newton et al., 2017). A recent study of sediment cores from the trough suggests deglaciation of the mid-shelf occurred probably around 13.4 cal. ka BP that was most likely driven by a northward advection of warmer Atlantic waters during the Bølling–Allerød (Weiser et al., 2023). However, no estimate is available for when (presumed) shelf edge deglaciation began. Like the larger Melville trough to the north, a small 'hook' type feature is present on the northern side of the trough mouth, below the main trough moraine. We focused our efforts into four stations along a west-east depth transect.

Figure 7. Regional map of operations of Stations 11 through 14 in Upernavik Trough Mouth Fan. Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. Multibeam depths are overlaid on the background bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Summary

At 10:37 UTC on July 20th, 2023 through 04:10 UTC on August 3rd, 2023, we surveyed and conducted over-the-side operations in the Upernavik TMF system. During surveying, Knudsen chirp, and at least one of the multibeam sonars were used. 12 total XBTs and CTD casts were applied to the multibeam systems for this region for sound velocity accuracy. Based on the bathymetry, this region appeared to be similar to, but a smaller version of, the Melville Bugt “hook” system and we again imaged several ridge features that followed along bathymetric contours over long distances. However, there were also some more prominent contour-parallel ridge type features and the major feature we imaged in this system was an abrupt transition from a smooth bathymetry in deeper water to a rougher hummocky looking topography higher on the slope. In cross section this looked somewhat like a basket of eggs and we colloquially referred to this topography as “eggland” on the ship. Within this rougher topography region we also imaged down slope (cross-contour) elongate features that occurred in parallel batches of 4-8 ridges. Coring operations in the region focused on the contrasting environments between the laminated, continuous reflectors located in deeper water and the rougher topography in shallower water. Several coring sites also focused on the elongate cross-contour features and targeted both the crest of the ridge features and the lows inbetween these features.

Station 11 Operations (AR2307-40PP/ZP through AR2307-45MC and AR2307-52GC through AR2307-53TC/JC)

Station 11 targeted an acoustically stratified sediment package on the slope at deeper depths than the region of rough hummocky bathymetry in the multibeam data. Chirp data resolved acoustically stratified reflectors that extended more than 30 m below the sea floor. A full station was implemented at Station 11.

Plankton tows AR2307-40PP/ZP and AR2307-41PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively and were followed by AR2307-42HC which was also successful, with all 21 bottles firing. The bottom depth was 1657 m (CTD altimeter) and the bottom water was taken at 1655 m (wire depth). Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths near the bottom (1655 m), at 1200, 1100, 900, 700, 500, 360, 300, 170, 100, 70, 45, 40, Chlorophyll maximum at 30, 20, 10, 5, and 1 m (see tables for bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a distinct peak at 34 m. Later PAM measurements showed that the 30 m samples represented indeed a Chlorophyll maximum.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.9	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.8	X	X	X			X	TRV
21	10	12.9	X	X				X	TRV
20	20	22.7	X	X	X			X	TRV
19	30 CM	34.2	X	X		X	X	X	TRV
18	40	42.9	X	X				X	TRV
13	45	47.7						X	TRV
11	100	102.4	X	X					TRV
8	300	302.1		X					TRV
7	360	361.9		X					TRV
6	500	501.4		X					TRV
5	700	700.6		X					TRV
4	900	900.3		X					TRV
2	1200	1199.9		X					TRV
1	1655	1652.8		X					TRV

Table 16: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-42HC. CM = Chlorophyll Max.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.9		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.8	X	X	X	X	ACM
21	10	12.9		X	X	X	ACM
20	20	22.7		X	X	X	ACM
19	30 Chlmax	34.2	X	X	X	X	ACM
18	40	42.9		X	X	X	ACM
13	45	47.7		X	X	X	ACM
12	70	72.9	X	X	X	X	ACM
11	100	102.4		X	X	X	ACM
9	170	172.3	X	X	X	X	ACM
8	300	302.1		X	X	X	ACM
7	360	361.9		X	X	X	ACM
6	500	501.4		X	X	X	ACM
5	700	700.6	X	X	X	X	ACM
4	900	900.3	X	X	X	X	ACM
3	1100	100.1	X	X	X	X	ACM
2	1200	1199.9		X	X	X	ACM
1	1655	1652.8	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 17: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-42HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
23	5	7.8		X
13	45	47.7		X
9	170	172.3		X
7	360	361.9		X
5	700	700.6		X
2	1200	1199.9		X
1	1655	1652.8		X
2	1560	1558.2		X
1	1638	1637.4		X

Table 18: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-42HC.

AR2307-43GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2466 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was on the pipe to just below the weight stand. AR2307-43GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 403 cm of sediments. AR2307-44TC/JC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core with a 10 ft trigger core. AR2307-44JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 18,650 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud up over the weight stand and in the flapper valve, the piston core had mud on the pipe to within a few feet of the weight. The coring pipe was caked in clayey mud around half an inch thick along the entire length of the barrel. AR2307-44TC recovered 275.9 cm of sediments in two sections. CT scans revealed that the lower half of Section 2 was a repeated section as a result of a recore following recoil and relaxation of the wire. AR2307-44JC had almost two full sections of water at the top of the liner, recovered 1448.7 cm of sediments, and was cut into 10 sections. A large cavity is visible in section 9 in the CT scan and another void was present in section 10, but this was closed on deck. CT scans also showed some coring deformation at the base of section 10.

Alan Mix eagerly waits to see how many zooplankton were in the water column. Maybe some *Neoglobergina pachyderma*--if he is lucky! Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

AR2307-45MC was rigged with 8 multicore tubes and a GoPro camera, but issues with the camera while deployed meant no recording was available. Bottom contact was made at 20 m/min as we were concerned the bottom was soft and the corer would overpenetrate. All eight multicore tubes returned with sediment ranging from 0.36 – 0.47 m, but only three of eight had clear water surfaces. Three tubes were archived (MC2, MC6, MC8), and two tubes were bagged in 5 cm intervals (MC1, MC4). Three tubes were sampled at sea for pore water using rhizons (MC5), biomarkers and foraminifera (MC3), and biology and neodymium (MC7) with the remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals. The deck was secured, and we surveyed out of the area.

After operations at Stations 12 and 13 we returned to Station 11 to take two cores ~2 nmi WNW of the previous deployments to capture an expanded upper sediment package. AR2307-52GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2350 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was on the pipe to just below the weight stand. AR2307-52GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 425.1 cm of sediments. AR2307-53TC/JC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core with a 10 ft trigger core. AR2307-53JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 18,600 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud up over the weight stand and the piston core had mud on the pipe to the base of the weight. The coring pipe was caked in clayey mud around half an inch thick along the entire length of the barrel. AR2307-53TC recovered 253.6 cm of sediments in two sections. AR2307-53JC recovered 1562.3 cm of sediments, and was cut into 11 sections. The deck was again secured, and we prepared for an overnight survey.

Fog was a common feature of our days in Baffin Bay and made for a chilly morning on deck. Robert Kelleher, Erin Gregory, & Megan Siragusa brave the elements and process a multicore for archiving. Photo Credit: M.D. Siragusa.

Station 12 Operations (AR2307-46GC through AR2307-49GC)

Station 12 targeted a linear elongated, downslope orientated, ridge type feature on the seafloor at ~1200 mwd that was imaged in the geophysical data. AR2307-46GC and AR2307-49GC were taken in the deeper acoustically stratified area on the north of the feature, AR2307-47GC and AR2307-48GC were taken on the crest of the feature.

AR2307-46GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2200 lbs of pull-out tension. The weight stand had not been rinsed down since the last deployment, so it was unclear if mud was on the weight stand, but mud was almost all the way up the pipe. AR2307-46GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 423.5 cm of sediments. We immediately ran Section 3 in the CT scanner to help make a decision whether to target the sequence with a longer core. In the meantime, we rigged AR2307-47GC as a 10 ft Armstrong gravity core that was deployed with a USBL on the crest of the feature. The core had a pull-out tension of 2150 lbs and corer returned with mud on top of the weight stand, and mud came out of the pin holes when the liner was removed from the corer. AR2307-47GC was cut into 2 sections and contained 290.6 cm of sediments. AR2307-48GC was rigged as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity core and deployed in the same location, again with a USBL to target the crest of the feature. It had a pull-out tension of 2450 lbs and returned with mud to below the weight stand. AR2307-48GC was cut into 4 sections and contained 493.8 cm of sediments.

The piston corer was assembled horizontally along the starboard rail before being lowered by the crane to its vertical position and load transferred to the A-frame for deployment. Taglines help control this process and a quick release line frees the barrel from the crane once the corer has rotated into position. Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

AR2307-49GC was a 30 ft gravity core heavy that used the piston core weight and was deployed from the A-frame on the trawl wire. It aimed to get deeper than AR2307-46GC and target a reflector in the Chirp data at about 7 meters. AR2307-49GC hit the seafloor at 40 m/min, had a pull-out tension of 16,000lbs and returned with mud ~5 ft below the bomb. Sediments were pointed at the end of the core cutter and were bagged separately, the core cutter was extruded into a spare piece of pipe and kept oriented. The lower most part of the core was extremely hard and was very poorly sorted. AR2307-49GC was cut into 6 sections and contained 667.7 cm of sediments. The decision was made not to split AR2307-49GC at sea so shear strength measurements could be made under controlled conditions in the laboratory at a later time.

Station 13 Operations (AR2307-50GC through AR2307-51GC)

Station 13 targeted the rough bathymetry to the west of Station 11 with two gravity cores. AR2307-50GC was a 30 ft gravity core heavy that used the piston core weight and was deployed from the A-frame on the trawl wire. It hit the seafloor at 40 m/min, had a pull-out tension of 12,500lbs and returned with mud ~5 ft below the bomb. AR2307-50GC was cut into 6 sections and contained 641.9 cm of sediments. AR2307-51GC was rigged as a 15ft Armstrong gravity corer and deployed in the same location. It had a pull-out tension of 2250 lbs, was cut into 4 sections, and contained 409.3 cm of sediments.

Station 14 Operations (AR2307-54PP/ZP through AR2307-58MC)

Station 14 targeted a thin sediment package in shallow water where the overlying drape meets the harder underlying seafloor. The wind was blowing at 10-15 kt meaning that sea ice was constantly drifting onto the station. We drifted with the ice over the station for deployments AR2307-54PP/ZP through AR2307-57GC and moved 0.5 – 1 nmi away into open water for AR2307-58MC. Plankton tows AR2307-54PP/ZP and AR2307-55PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively and were followed by AR2307-56HC which was deployed with the MISO camera and was also successful with all 21 bottles firing. The bottom depth was 878 m, and the bottom water was taken at the deepest point of the CTD cast (nominal 872 m). Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths near the bottom (872), at 700, 300, 200, 100, 60, Chlorophyll maximum at 40, 30, 25, 20, 10, 5, and 1 m (see tables for bottle depths).

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.4	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.5	X	X	X			X	TRV
22	10	12.5	X	X				X	TRV
21	20	22.4	X	X	X			X	TRV
17	25	27.4	X	X	X			X	TRV
13	30	32.3	X	X				X	TRV
10	40 CM	37.3	X	X		X	X	X	TRV
9	60	62.4	X	X					TRV
8	100	102.1	X	X					TRV
7	200	201.9		X		X			TRV
3	300	301.6		X					TRV
2	700	698.4		X					TRV
1	880	871.7		X					TRV

Table 19: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-56HC. CM = Chlorophyll Maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.4		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.5	X	X	X	X	ACM
22	10	12.5		X	X	X	ACM
21	20	22.4		X	X	X	ACM
17	25	27.4		X	X	X	ACM
13	30	32.3		X	X	X	ACM
10	40	37.3		X	X	X	ACM
9	60	62.4	X	X	X	X	ACM
8	100	102.1		X	X	X	ACM
7	200	201.9		X	X	X	ACM
3	300	301.6	X	X	X	X	ACM
2	700	698.4	X	X	X	X	ACM
1	880	871.7	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 20: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-56HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
17	25	27.4	X	
10	40	37.3	X	
3	300	301.6	X	

Table 21: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-56HC.

AR2307-57GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2250 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was approximately halfway up the outside of the pipe. AR2307-57GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 2 sections, and contained 227.7 cm of sediments.

AR2307-58MC was rigged with 8 multicore tubes and a GoPro camera. Bottom contact was made at 40 m/min. The GoPro camera showed that the multicorer penetrated successfully, but when the corer lifted from the seafloor most of the feet did not fully deploy and sediment was free to fall from most of the tubes during recovery. Six of the eight multicore tubes returned with sediment depths ranging from 0.36 – 0.50 m, four of those had clear water surfaces. Two tubes were archived (MC1, MC4) and three tubes were sampled at sea for porewater using rhizons (MC5), biomarkers and foraminifera (MC2), and biology (MC7) with the remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals. The deck was secured, and we surveyed out of the area and began a transit to Uummanaq TMF.

For summaries of the preliminary results from the CTD and underway data from Station 11 through 13, please refer to the information in Appendix 2. For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core description summaries associated with these three stations, please refer to the images and information in Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

Mag lines are sharpie lines scribed onto the outside of the core liner to ensure consistent splitting of sections downcore and they help the paleomagnetists orient the cores relative to one another. The ability to draw a straight line is not one that comes easy to some people – here Paul Walczak had attempted to help out. These liners are loaded into the piston core or used as they are to take shorter gravity cores. Some call the latter a sewer pipe core, but we call it the Armstrong gravity core – or the WHOI GC—regardless, it took great cores.

Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

*Some of the cores were quite stunning, while others were just homogenous mud. Here, Lindsey Monito is describing a stunning one with lots of color variation. Better get out the Munsell color chart!
Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.*

Ummannaq TMF (Stations 15 – 19)

Ummannaq trough meets the shelf break at ~600 mwd and upper slope sedimentation is dominated by stacked glacigenic debris flows (Dowdeswell et al., 2014; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2013b). A short (< 6 m) vibrocore below the shelf-trough mouth captures a shift from debris flows to IRD-free hemipelagic sediments associated with grounding zone retreat and the retention of a fringing ice shelf at ~17.1 cal ka BP (Jennings et al., 2017). Multiple grounding zone wedges have been identified in the Ummannaq trough mark that have been interpreted to mark still-stands during ice retreat. A small basin seaward of the main YD moraine, but landward of a moraine ridge dated to ~14.8 ka in core JR175-VC45 (Dowdeswell et al., 2014; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2013b; Sheldon et al., 2016) and offered an opportunity to recover a high-resolution deglaciation record from the shelf to complement the deeper LGM and early deglacial records from the more distal margins of the TMF. Seaward of the trough at the shelf break JR175-VC46 contains the most complete record of deglaciation from the trough mouth perspective, showing the transition to ice free conditions from ~17 ka (Jennings et al., 2017).

Stations 15 through 17 focused on the northern portions of the TMF. Station 18 was located at the trough mouth and stations 19 aimed to sample sediments from within the trough basin itself.

Figure 8. Regional map of operations of Stations 15 through 19 in Ummannaq Trough Mouth Fan (15 – 17) and Ummannaq Trough (18 and 19). Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. The background bathymetry is from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Survey

We conducted surveys or over-the-side operations from 13:39 UTC on August 3rd, 2023, to around 14:30 UTC on August 7th, 2023. 7 total XBTs and CTDs were applied to the multibeam systems for surveying in the region. During surveying, Knudsen chirp, and at least one of the multibeam sonars were used. The survey was focused on the slope north of the trough mouth fan and then some surveying was conducted in the trough itself, while transiting between sediment packages of interest. As similar transitional boundary between smoother seafloor in deeper water and rougher topography in shallower water as observed in the Upernavik system was again evident. In this system the transition ranged from ~1320 mwd in the northern part of the survey to ~1260 mwd in the south; the 60 m deepening to the north occurred over ~25 km. This rougher “eggland” type topography was primarily composed of ridges with similar morphology to those in the Upernavik Trough Hook. In shallower water there were several locations where sediments of deeper thicknesses had accumulated; one area was ~780 mbsl and the other was ~950 mbsl, both were targeted for coring. The contour parallel ridges were quite uniform in nature, and were overprinted, in some places, by other features that appeared less organized e.g. iceberg scours. Additionally, there were two features oriented at about 30° west of north. These seemed to be controlling larger-scale variation in the seafloor and did not seem related to the overlying sediment cover. The working hypothesis is that they are related to extensional faults that have been mapped in this region (Funck et al., 2012).

A clear day gives time for a quick photo op. Joe Stoner, Brendan Reilly, Cara Fritz, and Paul Walczak are just about ready to head inside for cheese thirty after they finished loading the piston corer for its next deployment.

Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

Station 15 Operations (AR2307-59PP/ZP through AR2307-66GC and AR2307-75GC through AR2307-76TC/JC).

Station 15 targeted acoustically stratified sediments just below a change in slope at about 1600 mwd. This is a similar looking sediment package to the deeper sites sampled at Melville Bugt and Upernavik at around the same depth. The wind and seas were relatively calm, so we could hold station throughout all operations at Station 15. Plankton tows AR2307-59PP/ZP and AR2307-60PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively and were followed by AR2307-61HC which was deployed with the MISO camera and was also successful, with all 21 bottles firing.

The bottom depth was 1597 m (CTD altimeter) and the bottom water was taken at 1580 m (wire depth). Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths near the bottom (1580 m), over the bottom turbidity peak at 1400, at 1200, 900, 600, 500, 300, 200, 100, 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, Chlorophyll maximum at 10, 5, and 1 m (see tables for bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a distinct peak at 20 m on the downcast, but got adjusted to 10 m wire depth on the way up. Later PAM measurements showed that the 10 m samples represented a Chlorophyll maximum.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.8	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.8	X	X	X			X	TRV
21	10 CM	12.8	X	X		X	X	X	TRV
20	20	15.7	X	X	X			X	TRV
19	30	32.7	X	X				X	TRV
18	40	42.8	X	X				X	TRV
13	50	52.7						X	TRV
12	60	62.6	X	X					TRV
11	100	102.4	X	X					TRV
9	200	202.3		X					TRV
7	300	301.9		X					TRV
6	500	501.1		X					TRV
5	600	600.7		X					TRV
4	900	899.9		X					TRV
2	1400	1398.5		X					TRV
1	1580	1592		X					TRV

Table 22: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-61HC. CM = Chlorophyll maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.8		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.8	X	X	X	X	ACM
21	10	12.8		X	X	X	ACM
20	20	15.7		X	X	X	ACM
19	30	32.7		X	X	X	ACM
18	40	42.8		X	X	X	ACM
13	50	52.7		X	X	X	ACM
12	60	62.6	X	X	X	X	ACM
11	100	102.4		X	X	X	ACM
9	200	202.3		X	X	X	ACM
7	300	301.9	X	X	X	X	ACM
6	500	501.1		X	X	X	ACM
5	600	600.7		X	X	X	ACM
4	900	899.9		X	X	X	ACM
3	1200	1199.4	X	X	X	X	ACM
2	1400	1398.5		X	X	X	ACM
1	1580	1592	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 23: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-61HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
23	5	7.8		X
13	50	52.7		X
7	300	301.9		X
5	600	600.7		X
2	1400	1398.5		X
1	1580	1592		X

Table 24: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-61HC.

AR2307-62GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2220 lbs of pull-out tension. The corer returned to the surface with the wire wrapped around the head of the corer. Mud was up on the weight stand and on removal of the coring pipe from the gravity corer approximately 20 cm of mud (core top) fell from the metal coupler to the weight stand. This material was bagged separately. AR2307-62GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 447 cm of sediments.

Sometimes core recovery doesn't go quite as planned, here the wire had wrapped itself around the head of the Armstrong gravity corer. Luckily for us we had a great Bosun and crew of Marine Technicians who quickly thought on their feet of how to sort it out! Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield

AR2307-63JC/TC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core. AR2307-62JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 16,300 lbs of pull-out tension. On return to the surface, it became clear that the trigger arm had sheared through during operations and that the trigger core and trigger line were not recovered. The piston core had mud along the entire length of the barrel up to the base of the bomb. AR2307-63JC recovered 1538.7 cm of sediments and was cut into 12 sections. CT scans later revealed that a large part of AR2307-63JC had experienced coring deformation. AR2307-64MC was rigged with 8 multicore tubes and a GoPro camera. Bottom contact was made at 20 m/min. All eight multicore tubes returned with sediment however, one was disturbed (MC1) and two had cloudy disturbed water columns that were opaque (MC3, MC6); they were not retained. The remaining five cores had lengths ranging from 0.41-0.51 m. Only one multicore tube had a clear water surface (MC7) and was sampled for foraminifera and biomarkers. The other four had varying degrees of cloudy water on the sediment and were either archived (MC2, MC8) or sampled for porewater using rhizons (MC4) or biology and neodymium (MC5). The remaining sediment from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals.

The ship was moved 2 nmi west to slightly shallower water to target the same sediment package above a break in slope. AR2307-65GC was rigged as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity core as the 15ft-rigged AR2307-62GC core had over penetrated. The corer returned to the surface with mud on the weight stand and mud/muddy water sloshed out of the top of the core when retrieving it to the ship. The pipe was full of mud and in order to keep the pipe vertical it had to be capped from the winch platform. AR2307-65GC was cut into 4 sections, and contained 577.4 cm of sediments. AR2307-66GC was rigged as a 30 ft gravity core heavy using the piston core weight and was deployed from the A-frame on the trawl wire. AR2307-66GC hit the seafloor at 30 m/min, had a pull-out tension of 13,900lbs and returned with mud on the pipe to below the bomb. Sediments were pointed at the end of the core cutter and were cut prior to removal of the core cutter and the core cutter sample. The two pieces were reassembled in a small piece of offcut liner as a stratigraphically intact core catcher sample. AR2307-66GC was cut into 6 sections and contained 806.3 cm of sediments.

Following stations 16 and 17 we returned to station 15 to recore at the site of AR2307-63JC as CT-scans had shown it to suffer from coring disturbance. AR2307-75GC was rigged as a 20 ft gravity core as AR2307-62GC had over penetrated. Bottom contact was made at 120 m/min and had 2600 lbs of pull-out tension. The corer returned to the surface with mud to the base of the weight stand. AR2307-75GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 4 sections, and contained 568.4 cm of sediments. AR2307-76JC/TC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core, hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 19,400 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud on the top of the weight stand and had mud in the flapper valve. The piston core had mud along the entire length of the barrel and midway up the bomb. AR2307-76TC recovered 146.3 cm of sediments and was 1 section. AR2307-76JC recovered 1547.6 cm of sediments and was cut into 11 sections. The deck was secured, and we began a survey out of the area. CT scans later revealed that AR2307-76JC had also experienced severe coring deformation.

Station 16 Operations (AR2307-67PP/ZP through AR2307-73GC)

Station 16 targeted an acoustically laminated sediment package at ~800 mwd on the upper slope at a transition where shallower deposits transform into rougher topography. Plankton tows AR2307-67PP/ZP and AR2307-68PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively and were followed by AR2307-69HC which was successfully deployed with the MISO camera and all 21 bottles fired.

The bottom depth was 785 m, and the bottom water was taken at the deepest point of the CTD cast (775 m). The remaining Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths of 700, 320, 200, 100, 60, 40, Chlorophyll maximum at 30, 25, 20, 10, 5, 1 m (see tables for bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a distinct peak at 32 m, with a second shallower Chl Maximum at about 22 m. Only the deeper Chl Max was sampled as Chl Max.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable isotopes. Samples in the upper 320 m were taken for biomarkers and samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.5	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.5	X	X	X			X	TRV
22	10	12.3	X	X				X	TRV
21	20	22.5	X	X	X			X	TRV
17	25	27.5	X	X	X			X	TRV
13	30 CM	32.4	X	X		X	X	X	TRV
10	40	42.3	X	X				X	TRV
9	60	62.4	X	X					TRV
8	100	101.2	X	X					TRV
7	200	202.1		X					TRV
3	320	321.7		X		X			TRV
2	700	700.1		X					TRV
1	775	778.9							TRV

Table 25: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-69HC. CM = Chlorophyll maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.5		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.5		X	X	X	ACM
22	10	12.3		X	X	X	ACM
21	20	22.5		X	X	X	ACM
17	25	27.5		X	X	X	ACM
13	30	32.4		X	X	X	ACM
10	40	42.3		X	X	X	ACM
9	60	62.4		X	X	X	ACM
8	100	101.2		X	X	X	ACM
7	200	202.1		X	X	X	ACM
3	320	321.7		X	X	X	ACM
2	700	700.1		X	X	X	ACM
1	775	778.9	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 26: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-69HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
23	25	27.5	X	
13	30	32.4	X	
7	320	321.7	X	

Table 27: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-69HC.

AR2307-70GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 1939 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was up on the weight stand and on removal of the coring pipe from the gravity corer approximately 15 cm of mud (core top) fell from the metal coupler to the weight

stand. This material was bagged separately. AR2307-70GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 446.9 cm of sediments.

AR2307-71JC/TC was rigged as a 40 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core. It was shorter than the 60 ft piston corer that we had been routinely operating due to the presence of a hard bottom reflector in the chirp image of the site. AR2307-71JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 17,500 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud below the weights, the piston core had mud on top of the weight. AR2307-71TC recovered 217.8 cm of sediments and was cut into 2 sections. During processing of AR2307-71JC a 1.25 m void was closed in the lowermost section and water drained from the core liner. AR2307-71JC recovered 1067.1 cm of sediments and was cut into 8 sections. AR2307-72MC was rigged with 8 multicore tubes and a GoPro camera. Bottom contact was made at 20 m/min. All eight multicore tubes returned with sediment however, one returned with an opaque turbid water (MC3) and was not retained. The remaining seven cores had lengths ranging from 0.36-0.43 m. Five multicore tubes had clear water surfaces and were sampled for foraminifera and biomarkers (MC2), porewaters using rhizons (MC4), and biology (MC8), the remaining two were archived (MC1, MC7). The remaining two cores had good sediment water interfaces and were archived (MC5) and again sampled for biology (MC6). The remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals. AR2307-73GC was rigged as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity corer and was deployed as AR2307-70GC over penetrated. AR2307-73GC made bottom contact at 120 m/min, had 2100 lbs of pull-out tension, was cut into 4 sections, and contained 581.0 cm of sediments.

Station 17 Operations (AR2307-74GC)

Station 17 was close to Station 16 (~5 nmi) and targeted a similar sediment package as found at Station 16 but was approximately 200 m deeper at 973 mwd. Only one core (AR2307-74GC) was taken at Station 17. AR2307-74GC was rigged as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity core. The corer returned to the surface with mud up to the weight stand. AR2307-74GC was cut into 4 sections, and contained 527.5 cm of sediments.

Station 18 Operations (AR2307-77GC)

Station 18 was designed to core near JR175-VC46, a core that was shown to have conformable sediments overlying diamict that extend back to ~17 ka by Jennings et al. (2017). We identified a similar sediment package in the Chirp data, and rigged a 15 ft Armstrong gravity corer as JR175-VC46 had ~2.7 m of sediments overlying 3 m of massive diamict. AR2307-77GC made bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 1820 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was approximately 2/3 of the way up the coring pipe, suggesting the corer stopped short of full recovery. AR2307-77GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 2 sections, and contained 280.3 cm of sediments. No diamict was recovered in the core or core catcher suggesting that either the corer didn't penetrate this layer, or it did, and it was lost on recovery to the ship. Either way, the basal contact observed in JR175-VC46 was not immediately identifiable in AR2307-77GC.

Station 19 Operations (AR2307-78GC through AR2307-80GC)

Ice coverage was more extensive in the trough than on the outer trough or TMF and made both access to stations and maintaining position on station difficult. Station 19 targeted an acoustically

stratified package overlying a basal reflector to the west of a feature interpreted to be a grounding zone wedge hypothesized to reflect a Younger Dryas still stand (Sheldon et al., 2016b). Based on the difficulty in recovering diamict with AR2307-77GC, AR2307-78GC was rigged as a 30 ft gravity core heavy that used the piston core weight and was deployed from the A-frame on the trawl wire. It aimed to punch into the dark attenuating reflector identified in the chirp data about 6m below the seafloor. AR2307-78GC hit the seafloor at 50 m/min, had a pull-out tension of 14,590lbs and returned with mud just above the third (uppermost) pipe indicating ~20ft penetration. The lower most part of the core was relatively soft, but contained large clasts and was very poorly sorted. CT-scans show a sharp transition to a large clast supported matrix in the bottom 20 cm of the core. AR2307-78GC was cut into 3 sections and contained 430.6 cm of sediments. AR2307-79GC was rigged as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core, made bottom contact at 120 m/min, and had 1849 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was up to the base of the weight stand and the pipe was full of sediment to the coupler. AR2307-79GC was cut into 3 sections and contained 443.5 cm of sediments. CT-scans showed that it had some overlap with AR2307-78GC but didn't access the basal high density interval. AR2307-80GC targeted where the deposit thinned to provide shallower access to the hard basal reflector and was rigged as a 20 ft gravity core heavy that used the piston core weight. Sea ice made it impossible to deploy over the ideal location and forced the ship to drift with the sea ice rather than hold station. By the time we had deployed the corer we had drifted over an area where the deposit had thickened to 7-8 m. AR2307-80GC hit at 50 m/min and had a pull out tension of 11,000 lbs. Mud was on top of the bomb and on the trawl wire suggesting over penetration of the corer. Sediments at the base of the core cutter felt a little stiffer than the other two sites at this station but didn't appear to contain any noticeable clasts like AR2307-78GC. AR2307-80GC was cut into 4 sections and contained 583.8 cm of sediments.

For summaries of the preliminary results from the CTD and underway data from Station 15 through 19, please refer to the information in Appendix 2. For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core description summaries associated with these five stations, please see Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

*Keenan Foley directing operations while Keith Shadle, Dan Wildrick, and Nick Mathews secure the piston core.
Photo Credit: R.G. Hatfield*

Paloma Olarte sampling Niskin bottles for neodymium. The water will get transferred to cube containers and then filtered over the next couple days. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

Disko Bay TMF (Stations 20 – 24)

The Disko cross-shelf trough has a more complex geometry than the other major troughs along the margin. Manifested as extreme differences in trough depth and a dog-leg configuration in plan form, the trough mouth meets the shelf break in 350-400 mwd on the south side of the fan (Hofmann et al., 2018b). Bathymetric mapping suggests the main shelf trough was overlain by thin ice that may have alternated between floating and grounded ice during the last glaciation (Hofmann et al., 2018, 2016). A brief Younger Dryas (YD) readvance to the shelf edge overprinted LGM morphologies (Hogan et al., 2016; Jennings et al., 2014; Ó Cofaigh et al., 2018, 2013a, 2013b), while several trough-bound grounding zone wedges indicate interrupted ice retreat from the shelf edge (Hogan et al., 2016).

Shelf-edge gullies connect to channels on the upper TMF surface, indicating the importance of glacier meltwater processes in the delivery of sediments to the upper Disko TMF (Ó Cofaigh et al., 2018). Seaward TMF sediments become increasingly acoustically stratified, comprising turbidites, hemipelagic sediments and IRD (Ó Cofaigh et al., 2018). The northern fringes of the Disko TMF comprise hemipelagic sediments and have shown to preserve integrated ocean and ice sheet records (Jackson et al., 2017; Jennings et al., 2018, 2017).

Figure 9. Regional map of operations of Stations 20 through 24 in Disko Bugt Trough Mouth Fan. Deployments are numbered and discriminated by symbol. Multibeam depths are overlaid on the background bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean IBCAO (Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Geophysical Summary

We conducted surveys and over-the-side operations in the Disko trough mouth fan slope region between 06:55 UTC on August 7th, 2023 and around 10:00 UTC on August 11th, 2023. Surveys used the Knudsen chirp and at least one of the multibeam sonars. We applied 6 XBTs and 2 CTD casts to the multibeam sonars for sound velocity during this time period. On the deeper slope we encountered sediment packages with deep acoustic penetration, continuous reflectors and units with even thickness. We observed over 40 m into the subbottom in some areas. These acoustically laminated sediments were the focus of most of the coring operations in this region. We were also interested in finding a shallow site for coring. Most of the shallow region was quite barren of sediment, but there were a set of structural ridges that trapped sediment and had some acoustically stratified reflectors. These deposits were not particularly thick (~5m max), but provided the best option to access shallow water sediment packages given the challenges we had surveying under the heavy sea ice we encountered in this region. These sediments contained high gas concentrations that caused sediment expansion after the cores were recovered. Additional surveying of the deeper region was conducted to map out the variation of the deep acoustically stratified sediments along the slope and to correlate them directly to the previously studied core, HU2008029-12PC (Jennings et al., 2018b, 2017b). After finishing the successful operations reported here and while trying to survey further south, sea ice conditions became too challenging to continue. At the request of the captain, we had to abandon our survey to the south and our anticipated operations for the final day planned in the region. Low visibility and thick sea ice was difficult to navigate and also prevented our ability to return to the region that we had previously surveyed and identified an alternative jumbo piston core location with enough time to conduct operations, leading us to end operations in the region and begin transit to Nuuk.

Cara Fritz, Lindsey Monito, and Jonas Donnenfield discuss the latest results from the multi-sensor track and CT scanner in the main lab. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

Station 20 Operations (AR2307-81PP/ZP through AR2307-87GC and AR2307-99TC/JC)

Station 20 targeted acoustically laminated sediments on the slope at ~1350 mwd. Plankton tows AR2307-81PP/ZP and AR2307-82PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively and were followed by AR2307-83HC which was deployed with the MISO camera and was also successful, with all 21 bottles firing.

The bottom depth was 1319 m (CTD altimeter) and the bottom water was taken at 1250 m (wire depth). Niskin bottles were triggered at nominal depths near the bottom (1250 m), over the bottom turbidity peak at 1000, 800, 600, 500, 400, 300, 200, 100, 75, 60, 50, 40, 30, 17, Chlorophyll maximum at 10, 5, and 1 m (see tables for bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a narrow peak at 18 m, with a second broad peak about 30 m. On the upcast the Chlorophyll maximum got adjusted to 10 m wire depth. Later PAM measurements showed that the 10 m samples represented indeed a Chlorophyll maximum.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3.4	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7.4	X	X	X			X	TRV
21	10 CM	17.4	X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
20	17	22.3	X	X				X	TRV
19	30	29.2	X	X				X	TRV
18	40	39.3	X	X				X	TRV
17	50	52.3	X	X				X	TRV
13	60	62.1	X	X					TRV
12	75	77.2	X	X					TRV
10	100	101.9	X	X					TRV
9	200	202		X					TRV
8	300	301.8		X					TRV
7	400	411.1		X					TRV
5	500	490.9		X					TRV
4	600	600.6		X					TRV
3	800	799.7		X					TRV
2	1000	1099.3		X					TRV
1	1250	1311.7		X					TRV

Table 28: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-83HC. CM = Chlorophyll maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3.4		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7.4		X	X	X	ACM
21	10	17.4		X	X	X	ACM
20	17	22.3		X	X	X	ACM
19	30	29.2		X	X	X	ACM
18	40	39.3		X	X	X	ACM
17	50	52.3		X	X	X	ACM
13	60	62.1		X	X	X	ACM
12	75	77.2		X	X	X	ACM
10	100	101.9		X	X	X	ACM
9	200	202		X	X	X	ACM
8	300	301.8	X	X	X	X	ACM
7	400	411.1		X	X	X	ACM
5	500	490.9		X	X	X	ACM
4	600	600.6		X	X	X	ACM
3	800	799.7	X	X	X	X	ACM
2	1000	1099.3		X	X	X	ACM
1	1250	1311.7	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 29: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-83HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
23	5	7.4		X
12	75	77.2		X
7	400	411.1		X
5	500	490.9		X
3	800	799.7		X
1	1250	1311.7		X

Table 30: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-83HC.

AR2307-84GC was deployed as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2250 lbs of pull-out tension. Mud was up on the weight stand and on removal of the coring pipe from the gravity corer water and approximately 20-30 cm of mud (core top) sprayed out from the base of the metal coupler to the weight stand. AR2307-84GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 4 sections, and contained 592.3 cm of sediments.

AR2307-85JC/TC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core. AR2307-85JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 16,000 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud on the weights, the piston core had mud on top of the weight. AR2307-85TC recovered 278.4 cm of sediments and was cut into 2 sections. AR2307-85JC recovered 1692.8 cm of sediments and was cut into 12 sections. AR2307-86MC was rigged with 8 multicore tubes and a GoPro camera. Bottom contact was made at 20 m/min. All eight multicore tubes returned with sediment, 7 had clear water columns and one was slightly cloudy (MC6). Two core tubes had shrimp in them (MC4, MC5). Lengths ranged from 0.46-0.56 m

and were sampled for foraminifera and biomarkers (MC7), porewaters using rhizons (MC5), biology (MC3), and neodymium (MC6), and the remaining four were archived (MC1, MC2, MC4, MC8). The remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals. AR2307-87GC was rigged as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity corer to try and better capture the uppermost sediments as AR2307-84GC over penetrated. AR2307-87GC made bottom contact at the slower speed of 30 m/min, had 2200 lbs of pull-out tension, but also over penetrated. AR2307-87GC was cut into 4 sections, and contained 591.1 cm of sediments.

Following operations at stations 21 through 23 we returned to station 20 to both duplicate and extend AR2307-85JC/TC. AR2307-99JC/TC was rigged as a 70 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core and was deployed in the same location as AR2307-85JC/TC. AR2307-99JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 15,900 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud on the weights. The piston core had mud on top of the weight. AR2307-99TC recovered 241.3 cm of sediments and was cut into 2 sections. AR2307-99JC recovered 1954.4 cm of sediments and was cut into 14 sections.

Mud on the weights! Joe Stoner takes a look a trigger core that over penetrated. Better get that written on the coring datasheets! Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

Station 21 Operations (AR2307-88GC through AR2307-89TC/JC)

Station 21 was upslope of Station 20 and was positioned where the reflectors in the Chirp data thinned which allowed shallower access to more deeply buried sediments not accessible at Station 20. AR2307-88GC was deployed as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity core; bottom contact was made at 40 m/min to try and mitigate overpenetration and had 2250 lbs of pull-out tension. Approximately 2 – 3 m of mud fell from the base of the core during recovery from the water to the rail. We determined a rock likely damaged the core catcher, preventing it from providing resistance when the core was lifted from the ocean. AR2307-88GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 2 sections, and contained 173.9 cm of sediments.

AR2307-89JC/TC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core. AR2307-89JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 17,800 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud on the weights. AR2307-89TC recovered 266.5 cm of sediments and was cut into 2 sections. AR2307-89JC recovered 1710.9 cm of sediments and was cut into 12 sections.

Washing down the core with the firehose is a tough job, but someone has to do it. Megan Siragusa (left) and Jonas Donnenfield (right) clean the mud from the outside of recently recovered jumbo piston cores. Photo Credits: M.D. Siragusa and R.G. Hatfield.

Station 22 Operations (AR2307-90PP/ZP through AR2307-96MC)

Station 22 targeted a shallower sediment deposit than Stations 20 and 21 at ~700 mwd. Plankton tows AR2307-90PP/ZP and AR2307-91PP/ZP were deployed to 300 m and 60 m respectively and were followed by AR2307-92HC which was deployed with the MISO camera and was also successful, with all 21 bottles firing. The bottom depth was 695 m, and the bottom water was taken at the deepest point of the CTD cast (688 m). The remaining Niskin bottles were triggered at 500, 370, 200, 100, 60, 40, Chlorophyll maximum at 30, 25, 20, 10, 5, 1 m (see tables for bottle depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a broad peak from 20 to 50 m with a maximum at 33 m. Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable and radiogenic isotopes. Samples in the upper 370 m were taken for biomarkers and samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
24	1	3	X	X				X	TRV
23	5	7	X	X	X			X	TRV
22	10	11.9	X	X				X	TRV
21	20	21.9	X	X	X			X	TRV
17	25	26.9	X	X				X	TRV
13	30	32	X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
10	40	41.9	X	X				X	TRV
9	60	61.8	X	X					TRV
8	100	101.8	X	X					TRV
7	200	201.6		X					TRV
3	370	369.2		X		X			TRV
2	500	500.6		X					TRV
1	680	687.9		X					TRV

Table 31: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-83HC. CM = Chlorophyll maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
24	1	3		X	X	X	ACM
23	5	7		X	X	X	ACM
22	10	11.9		X	X	X	ACM
21	20	21.9		X	X	X	ACM
17	25	26.9		X	X	X	ACM
13	30	32		X	X	X	ACM
10	40	41.9		X	X	X	ACM
9	60	61.8		X	X	X	ACM
8	100	101.8		X	X	X	ACM
7	200	201.6		X	X	X	ACM
3	370	369.2	X	X	X	X	ACM
2	500	500.6		X	X	X	ACM
1	680	687.9	X	X	X	X	ACM

Table 32: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-83HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
17	25	26.9	X	
13	30	32	X	
3	370	369.2	X	

Table 33: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-83HC.

AR2307-93GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 1597 lbs of pull-out tension. The pipe returned to the ship cracked about halfway up the length, the core catcher fingers were inverted, and no mud was in the pipe. AR2307-94GC was deployed as a 10

ft Amrstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 1750 lbs of pull-out tension. AR2307-94GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 2 sections, and contained 259.4 cm of sediments.

AR2307-95GC was rigged as a 30 ft gravity core heavy that used the piston core weight and was deployed from the A-frame on the trawl wire. It aimed to punch into the basal reflector identified in the chirp data about 7.5 m below the seafloor. AR2307-95GC hit the seafloor at 60 m/min, had a pull-out tension of 9,400 lbs and returned with mud just above the third (uppermost) pipe indicating ~20ft penetration. AR2307-95GC was cut into 3 sections and contained 438.6 cm of sediments. As the bottom appeared hard in the Chirp image, AR2307-96MC was rigged with 4 multicore tubes and a GoPro camera. Bottom contact was made at 40 m/min. All four multicore tubes returned with sediment, and all had clear water columns. Lengths ranged from 0.23-0.40 m and were sampled for foraminifera and biomarkers (MC5), porewaters using rhizons (MC3), and phytoplankton (MC7); MC1 and MC3 were archived. The remaining sediment left over from sampling was bagged at 5 cm intervals.

AR2307-94GC and -95GC both smelled strongly of hydrogen sulfide while equilibrating in the MST/CT Van and it was considered unpleasant and unsafe to have them in that confined space. Accordingly, they were moved outside and kept on deck for around 2 days. While being moved, it was clear that the sediments were expanding and were pushing the end caps off. Holes were drilled in the end caps and along the core barrel to let the cores degas while sitting outside. Some sediment was pushed out of these holes while it degassed. Because this station seemed interesting for biogeochemical study, additional drill holes were made in AR2307-95GC away from the primary drill holes to sample pore waters using a rhizon sampler. Once the cores had finished degassing and had stopped smelling, they were returned to the MST/CT van and continued through normal core flow.

Nicknamed “The Stinky Cores” by the BADEX science team, AR2307-94GC and -95GC degassed considerably after recovery, as seen in this newly drilled hole to relieve pressure in AR2307-95GC. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

Station 23 Operations (AR2307-97GC through AR2307-98GC)

Station 23 targeted a sediment package at 900 mwd. AR2307-97GC was deployed as a 15 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 1820 lbs of pull-out tension. AR2307-97GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 3 sections, and contained 406.0 cm of sediments. AR2307-98GC was rigged as a 30 ft gravity core heavy that used the piston core weight and was deployed from the A-frame on the trawl wire. AR2307-95GC hit the seafloor at 60 m/min, had a pull-out tension of 10,000 lbs and returned with mud just above the third (uppermost) pipe indicating ~20ft penetration. AR2307-98GC was cut into 5 sections and contained 607.9 cm of sediments.

Station 24 Operations (AR2307-100GC through AR2307-101TC/JC)

Station 24 targeted sediments at ~1300 mwd, 13 nmi to the SW of station 20, on the north side of a basement high where a deep acoustically transparent unit thinned. AR2307-100GC was deployed as a 20 ft Armstrong gravity core with bottom contact at 120 m/min and had 2236 lbs of pull-out tension. The corer over penetrated as ~15 cm of the uppermost sediments fell from the metal coupler upon recovery. AR2307-100GC was recovered to the ship, cut into 4 sections, and contained 581.9 cm of sediments. AR2307-101JC/TC was rigged as a 60 ft piston core and 10 ft trigger core. Sea ice was thick and individual floes were drifting at over 1 kt so as we drifted with the ice we were pushed off the original target. However, the chirp data indicated that although we drifted into deeper water, we did not drift into a significantly different sediment package. AR2307-101JC/TC hit the bottom at 30 m/min and had 16,564 lbs of pull-out tension. The trigger core had mud on the weights, the piston core had mud on top of the weight. AR2307-101TC recovered 262.6 cm of sediments and was cut into 2 sections. AR2307-101JC recovered 1677.4 cm of sediments and was cut into 12 sections.

A piston core about to be landed along the starboard rail. It was always a challenge to hold station for piston coring operations when sea ice was around, but the captain and crew worked tirelessly to make it possible. Photo Credit: B.T. Reilly.

For summaries of the preliminary results from the CTD and underway data from Station 20 through 24, please refer to the information in Appendix 2. For chirp profiles, CT scans, line scan images, MSCL data, and core description summaries associated with these five stations, please see Appendix 3. For core description log sheets and coring data sheets, please see Appendixes 4 and 5.

Nuup Kangerlua (Stations 25 – 27)

Once sea ice forced us from station 24 in the Disko TMF we began an early transit to Port in Nuuk. This presented an opportunity for three more stations outside and within the Nuuk fjord system, Nuup Kangerlua. CTD profiles and hydrocasts were the only over the side operations at stations 25 through 27.

Station 25 Operations (AR2307-102HC)

Station 25 targeted the outermost part of Nuup Kangerlua where it meets the shelf and bifurcates into two systems to the north and to the south. A hydrographic time series of Nuup Kangerlua has been established along the full length of the fjord towards the shelf break of Fyllas Banke and maintained as an annual survey by the Greenland Climate Research Centre since 2008. The last transect was taken a few days before we arrived on station but did not reach the shelf due to limitations of small boat operations. AR2307-102HC represents a continuation of this transect, which will show the source of a potential summer bloom and the extend of inner fjord processes (e.g. subglacial upwelling) and was located in 245 mwd.

AR2307-102HC was deployed without the MISO camera and 21 bottles were successfully fired. The bottom water was taken at 200 m. Niskin bottles were triggered near the bottom (200 m) at 150, 100, 60, 40, Chlorophyll maximum at 30, 25, 20, 10, 5, and 1 m (wire depths). The Chlorophyll maximum was a broad peak at 32 m. Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable isotopes. Samples in the upper 200 m were taken for biomarkers and samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
	1		X	X				X	TRV
	5		X	X	X			X	TRV
	10		X	X				X	TRV
	20		X	X	X			X	TRV
	25		X	X				X	TRV
	30 CM		X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
	40		X	X				X	TRV
	60		X	X					TRV
	100		X	X					TRV
	150			X					TRV
	200			X		X			TRV

Table 34: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-102HC. CM = Chlorophyll maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
	1			X	X	X	ACM
	5			X	X	X	ACM
	10			X	X	X	ACM
	20			X	X	X	ACM
	25			X	X	X	ACM
	30			X	X	X	ACM
	40			X	X	X	ACM
	60			X	X	X	ACM
	100			X	X	X	ACM
	150			X	X	X	ACM
	200			X	X	X	ACM

Table 35: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-102HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
	10		X	
	30		X	
	200		X	

Table 36: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-102HC.

Station 26 Operations (AR2307-103HC)

Station 26 targeted the outer part of Nuup Kangerlua, but still within the fjord and inside the present day coastline. A hydrographic time series with monthly data was established in 2005 and is maintained by the Greenland Climate Research Centre. AR2307-103HC was located in 398 mwd and is close to one station along this existing transect. AR2307-103HC was deployed without the MISO camera and 21 bottles were successfully fired.

The bottom water was taken at 390 m. Niskin bottles were triggered near the bottom (390 m) at 350, 300, 200, 100, 60, 40, 30, 20, 10 Chlorophyll maximum at 5, and 1 m. The Chlorophyll maximum was a broad peak at about 10m, and was adjusted to 5m on the way up.

Samples in the entire water column were taken for nutrients and stable isotopes. Samples in the upper 300 m were taken for biomarkers and samples in the upper 100 m were taken for phytoplankton communities (microscopy), chlorophyll a measurements, and primary production estimates. Samples at the chlorophyll maximum were taken for DNA metabarcoding and a nutrient enrichment experiment in which nitrate, silicate, and phosphate were added for in situ incubations for three days to test for potential *in situ* nutrient limitations.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Chl a	Nutrients	Phytoplankton	DNA	Nutrient experiment	Primary production	Responsible
	1		X	X				X	TRV
	5 CM		X	X	X	X	X	X	TRV
	10		X	X				X	TRV
	20		X	X	X			X	TRV
	25		X	X				X	TRV
	30		X	X				X	TRV
	40		X	X				X	TRV
	60		X	X					TRV
	100		X	X					TRV
	200			X					TRV
	300			X		X			TRV
	350			X					TRV
	390			X					TRV

Table 37: Samples taken for phytoplankton diversity and ecology, cast AR2307-103HC. CM = Chlorophyll maximum.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	DIC D14C	DIC d13C	H2O d18O	Chlorinity	Responsible
	1			X	X	X	ACM
	5			X	X	X	ACM
	10			X	X	X	ACM
	20			X	X	X	ACM
	25			X	X	X	ACM
	30			X	X	X	ACM
	40			X	X	X	ACM
	60			X	X	X	ACM
	100			X	X	X	ACM
	200			X	X	X	ACM
	300			X	X	X	ACM
	350			X	X	X	ACM
	390			X	X	X	ACM

Table 38: Samples taken for isotope tracers and biogeochemistry, cast AR2307-103HC.

CTD #	Nominal m	Actual m	Biomarkers (RVK)	Neodymium (PO)
	5		X	
	10		X	
	300		X	

Table 39: Samples taken for Neodymium tracers and biomarkers, cast AR2307-103HC.

Station 27 Operations (AR2307-104HC through AR2307-109HC)

Station 27 was a series of six CTD casts that sampled a longstanding monitoring line by the government of Greenland. Full depth CTD casts were performed at each of the six locations (AR2307-104HC through AR2307-109HC). Bottom depths ranged from 45 m to 266 m. One water sample was taken at the Chlorophyll maximum at each of the six locations for nutrients and phytoplankton productivity. The CTD was secured, and we positioned south of the port awaiting docking at 10:00 UTC (08:00 local), and there was much rejoicing.

Janneke Wade de-Jong and Georg Koszulinski were the filmographers onboard BADEX. Watch out for BADEX documentaries coming to a big screen and a small screen near you! Photo Credit: K. Stelling.

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